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Completing Audio Drum Loops with Transformer Neural Networks

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Abstract

Infilling drums refers to complementing a drum pattern with additional drum events that are stylistically consistent with the loop. This task can be applied to computer-assisted composition; for instance, the composer can sketch some instrument parts of a drum beat and obtain the system’s suggestions for new parts. In this thesis, we present the Transformer Groove Infilling, a Transformer Neural Network approach to the infilling task. Until now, the infilling of drum beats has been implemented using Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) architectures, in particular, sequence-to-sequence models that employ LSTM cells. However, in such architectures, as a consequence of sequential computation, proximity is emphasized when dealing with dependencies in the input sequence. Furthermore, those models receive the audio loops as symbolic input sequences. In contrast, the Transformer Groove Infilling model is based on the Transformer architecture, which relies entirely on self-attention mechanisms to represent the input sequences, which allows for faster training since parallelization is possible. In addition, we present a novel direct audio representation that enables the Transformer Groove Infilling to receive the input drum loops in the audio domain, avoiding their transcription and tokenization.

We train several instances of the Transformer Groove Infilling model to perform the following infilling subtasks: the infilling of closed hi-hats, the infilling of both kicks and snares, and the infilling of a drum loop without an instrument constraint. For comparison purposes, we also trained an equivalent model with a symbolic input representation in order to highlight the efficiency of the audio representation proposed in this thesis.

Keywords: Infilling; Transformer; Drum generation.

Chapter 1

Introduction

In 1843, Augusta Ada King, the Countess of Lovelace, commonly known as Ada Lovelace, published the translation of an article on The Analytical Engine¹, an early automatic calculator. At the end of her translation, she appended her considerations on the machine under the title *Notes*, a rather cautious one for a manuscript that contained what is known as the first computer program. In this document, she writes:

[The Analytical Engine’s operating mechanism] might act upon other things besides number, were objects found whose mutual fundamental relations could be expressed by those of the abstract science of operations, and which should be also susceptible of adaptations to the action of the operating notation and mechanism of the engine. . . . Supposing, for instance, that the fundamental relations of pitched sounds in the science of harmony and of musical composition were susceptible of such expression and adaptations, the engine might compose elaborate and scientific pieces of music of any degree of complexity or extent.

– Ada Lovelace²

¹The Analytical Engine was designed by Charles Babbage and partially built by the time of his death in 1871 [1]. In her English translation of the article by the Italian engineer Luigi F. Menabrea (*Notions sur la Machine Analytique de M. Charles Babbage*, Bibliothèque Universelle de Genève, 41, 352–376.), Ada Lovelace appended her notes on the engine. The translation and the notes were published under the pseudonym AAL in Richard Taylor’s *Scientific Memoirs*, 3, art. 29, 666–731, under the title *Sketch of the Analytical Engine invented by Charles Babbage, Esq., by L. F. Menabrea of Turin, officer of the Military Engineers*, in August 1843 [2].

²Quoted in [2].

More than a century later, as Lovelace anticipated, the Illiac Suite (1956) was the first musical piece composed by a computer. Hiller and Isaacson, the authors of the program, hard-coded the rules of different compositional styles and decided on different elements of the composition by generating random numbers [3]. Computers have been proficient at addressing tasks that can be described by a set of rules and solved by applying a receipt or algorithm. The first great successes of Artificial Intelligence (AI), such as IBM’s Deep Blue, the chess-playing system that defeated world chess champion Kasparov in 1997, were based on this hard-coded knowledge [4].

Remembering large sets of chess strategies might be challenging for a human, yet not for a computer. In contrast, computers encounter great difficulty in tasks that are not easily encoded in rules, such as describing a picture. While computers only see numbers that represent the colors of a large number of pixels, humans see elements they can associate with their previous experiences. Deep learning techniques address these intuitive or hard to formally describe tasks by showing computers large amounts of data, providing them with the experience from which the solutions to such problems can be inferred. Born in the late 1960s, these techniques encountered several technical limitations in their first decades and lost the interest of the scientific community during the period popularly known as the AI winter. With the developments of hardware for computation, the deep learning field gained notoriety during the 2000s. After the successes in computer vision in the early 2010s, deep learning has expanded to a variety of fields, and in particular, music. The motivation behind the use of deep learning for music generation³ tasks lies in its generality [5]: in contrast to hard-coded or rule-based knowledge systems, a deep learning model can be used for generating different music styles or even solving different tasks.

In broad terms, automatic music generation systems can be classified by their ob-

³In this thesis, the term *generation* is used to refer to computer music generation as opposed to human performance or composition.

jective into two categories: systems that make music in an autonomous manner and systems that aim to assist human composition and performance [5]. Additionally, according to the level of music representation, they can also be divided into three main tasks: score, performance, and audio generation. The score generation tackles the symbolic and discrete representation of music and can deal with melody or accompaniment generation, polyphonic compositions, or style transfer, among others. The performance generation involves the expressive interpretation of a piece and adds dynamics and microtiming information to a given symbolic representation. Finally, audio generation addresses both of the latter while also dealing with continuous timbral information [6].

This thesis tackles the task of completing a given audio drum loop. As Bello et al. [7] define them, drum loops are “short, pre-recorded percussive riffs, which are digitally repeated, processed and edited to create the rhythmic section of a given track”. Perhaps the most known drum loop is the one replaying the drum break in ‘Amen, Brother’ (1969) by The Winston Brothers, which appears in hip-hop tracks such as ‘Words of Wisdom’ (1989) by Third Base or N.W.A’s ‘Straight Outta Compton’ (1989). With the emergence of samplers such as the Akai MPC (1988), which allowed playing sequenced prerecorded drum sounds, producers would chop those drum breaks to sample the sounds of each drum kit instrument and recombine them in new patterns. This became the percussive foundation of new electronic dance music sub-genres such as jungle or drum’n’bass [8]. The influence of the drum kit sounds in the twentieth Western music is emphasized by Brennan in his social history of the drum kit [8]:

Whether played on an acoustic kit, synthesized or sampled, the sounds of the drum kit have influenced almost every major genre of music from the twentieth century onwards. The drum kit, therefore, made a tremendous impact on Western classical music as well, eroding as it did the established boundaries between high and low art. Similarly, the drum kit’s presence was so pervasive that, for better or worse, it crept over time into indigenous genres where no drum kit had previously been used, from

Brazilian samba to Ghanaian highlife to South Korean popular song and beyond.

The MPC sampler was initially conceived as an “authentic-sounding facsimile of an acoustic drum kit through sequenced digital samples” [8], but the original and novel usages given to it by producers and artists gave rise to new musics and genres. A couple of decades earlier, in the early 1970s, hip-hop was reinventing turntables and transforming them into musical instruments, developing an own playing technique and musical culture [9, 10]. Although substantially different, the use of deep learning for music generation follows the tendency of using existing technologies for creating new musics.

In this thesis, we propose a deep learning system that completes an input drum loop in two different manners:

- (1) By adding one or more drum kit’s instrument parts that were not initially present in the drum loop.
- (2) By adding events⁴ (hits) to all (or part) of the instruments in the drum kit.

Both tasks are regarded in the literature as the *infilling* task [11, 12]. Since the system deals with the suggestion for new parts to a previously composed or performed drum pattern, it can be framed as an assistant to human composition or performance. As suggested by Ippolito et al. [12], infilling can be used by composers to select parts of their compositions to be rewritten by the system.

With regards to the music representation level, while the majority of the music generation systems operate in the symbolic domain [5], the system here proposed receives an audio drum loop as input and outputs a score with the suggested augmented parts. The choice of the audio domain for the input is motivated, on the

⁴In the context of this thesis, *event* refers to a percussive hit from a drum kit instrument at a particular instant of time.

one hand, by the extended usage of audio drum loops in popular music genres such as techno, hip hop, dub or drum and bass, among others [7]. These loops are usually shared online in audio format and reused by producers in their compositions. In order to deal with audio loops, a system with a symbolic input would require an intermediate layer of transcription, which is here avoided. On the other hand, an audio input also allows for using the system while composing with the physical analog (or electronic) drums. Finally, the audio domain contains more information (e.g. timbral and expressive) than its symbolic counterpart, which is a compressed representation of the former.

The infilling of a drum pattern by adding one or more drum instrument parts has been previously addressed in the work by Gillick et al. [11]. In their paper, Gillick et al. propose a model that operates in the symbolic domain, with both symbolic input and output sequences. Their model has an encoder-decoder architecture, with both the encoder and the decoder based on Recurrent Neural Networks. However, recurrent architectures pose several difficulties for learning long-range dependencies as well as result in long training times.

In this work, an infilling system based on the Transformer architecture [13] is proposed. The Transformer architecture was initially developed in the field of natural language processing, where it has gained great success with the Generative Pre-trained Transformer 3 (GPT-3) [14], a model that has reached the general audience due to the quality of its generated text⁵. The architecture has recently been adapted to the fields of computer vision, with the Vision Transformer [16], and audio processing, with the Audio Spectrogram Transformer (AST) [17], to name a few examples. Similarly to the architecture employed by Gillick et al. [11], the Transformer is an encoder-decoder architecture. However, in contrast to Gillick et al.'s model, the

⁵The first co-written book with GPT-3 has been published recently: *Pharmako-AI* by K Allado-McDowell [15], that collects several essays about various topics such as cosmology, memory or language.

Transformer does not use recurrence in order to deal with the sequential nature of the input and output objects. Instead, it is based on the attention mechanism, which results in a better ability to deal with long-range dependencies in the sequence. In the context of piano performances, an infilling system based on the Transformer architecture has been already proposed by Ippolito et al. [12]. Contrary to the model proposed in this thesis, Ippolito et al.’s model operates on the symbolic domain.

During the course of this thesis, several instances of the Transformer Infilling Model have been trained on specific tasks, such as the infilling of particular instrument parts (e.g., closed hi-hat or kick drum) or the infilling of loops that had random hits removed. Their performance is evaluated in terms of objective metrics that allow for objective comparison against other generative systems [18]. A symbolic version of one of the models is also trained in order to evaluate the suitability of the audio representation used for the Transformer Infilling Model audio input.

The remaining chapters of this thesis are organized as follows. In Chapter 2, the state of the art of deep music generation and in particular, expressive drumming performance generation, is presented. In Chapter 3, we discuss the methodology used for addressing the infilling of audio drum loops. The hyperparameter selection for each experiment is addressed in Chapter 4. The results and evaluation are considered in Chapter 5. Finally, we present this thesis conclusions in Chapter 6, as well as propose future approaches to the task of infilling audio drum loops.

Chapter 2

State of the art

In this chapter we present the relevant state of the art to this thesis in two parts. The first one, in Section 2.1, presents an overview of the existing related work using deep learning for music generation, with an emphasis on expressive and drum performance generation, as well as previous existing approaches to the infilling task. The second part discusses the deep learning architectures used in such generative systems (Section 2.2), and in particular, the Transformer Architecture (Section 2.3).

2.1 Deep music generation

Deep music generation refers to the generation of music with deep learning techniques [6]. At the time of writing, a recent and comprehensive state of the art on the subject, by Ji et al. [6], exists. While this survey covers the extensive field of deep music generation, for the purpose of this thesis, only the topics of expressive music performance generation and drum score generation are presented.

As it has been already introduced, in this thesis we develop a system based on the Transformer Architecture that performs the infilling task. The infilling task can be understood as a conditional drum pattern generation task, since it generates a

pattern (drum hits or instrument parts not present in the original drum pattern) given a different input pattern. Moreover, music generation tasks can be classified in three-level hierarchy [6]: the top level corresponds to score generation, while the bottom level corresponds to audio generation. An intermediate level between both can be inserted, corresponding to the performance generation. This hierarchy refers to the ability of the lower level to be conditioned by the higher level, e.g., generate the performance microtimings conditioned on the score. Performance generation adds dynamics and timing information to the rendered score, providing a more natural or human sound, while bottom-level audio generation usually focuses on the timbral aspects of the generated sound. For the purpose of this thesis, both top-level and middle-level tasks (score and performance generation) are of interest. In the following sections, an overview on their state of the art will be given.

2.1.1 Drum pattern generation

In contrast to melodic generation tasks, not many models focused solely on the generation of drum patterns have been developed. The existing models in the literature generate drums along with or conditioned by melodic parts. The Muse-GAN model, proposed by Dong et al. in 2017 [19], receives a track composed by a human as an input and generates a multi-track composition, including a drums track. In the context of generating drums for given melodies, Wei et al. [20] implement a model based on Variational Auto Encoders (VAEs), whereas the DeepDrum model, introduced by Makris et al. in 2019 [21], generates a drum pattern given a bass track that imposes some metrical constraints. None of these models focuses on adding drum parts to a given drum pattern or in generating expressive performances.

2.1.2 Expressive performance generation

Automatic performance generation tasks can be divided into two categories: rendering expressive performances from a given score, and generating the expressive

performance along with the score [6].

Long Short-Term Memory architectures (LSTMs) have been effectively used for rendering expressive piano performances. To name a few examples, the StyleGAN architecture [22] generates expressive dynamics for a given score, and the VirtuosoNet [23] uses a hierarchical architecture to generate expressive dynamics, tempo, articulation, and even pedaling. Figure 2.1, extracted from [6], shows a chronology of models addressing the generation of expressive performances. Except from the GrooVAE model [11], the rest of the models focus on piano performances. As Ji et al [6] suggest, the reason behind the expressive performance generation being mainly focused on piano is likely the availability of piano performance datasets in comparison to other instruments.

Figure 2.1: Chronology of deep learning models addressing expressive performance generation. Figure by Ji et al. [6].

Piano performance generation

The Performance-RNN architecture, proposed by Simon et al. in 2017 [24], used LSTM units for composing polyphonic piano pieces. The resulting performances were rich in expressiveness, but still, the compositions lacked long-term structure. Another LSTM-based approach by Oore et al. [25, 26] encounters similar problems.

The Transformer architecture, introduced in 2017 by Vaswani et al. [13], overcomes the difficulties of the Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) family of architectures

(including LSTMs) for dealing with long-term structures in music by using an architecture entirely based on the attention mechanism. With some modifications of the original Transformer regarding the positional encoding [27], The Music Transformer [28], proposed by Huang et al. is able to generate music with long-term structure. Choi et al. [29] used the Music Transformer to generate expressive performances in the same style as given performances. The Transformer-XL [30], a further improvement on the Transformer architecture that is able to capture dependencies between different fixed-length training examples, has been successfully implemented by Huang and Yang [31] for generating expressive pop piano compositions, and by Wu et al. [32] to generate baroque, classical and romantic piano performances.

Drum performance generation

In 2006, Wright and Berdahl [33] presented a system for modelling the microtiming for quantized Brazilian drumming piano-rolls with machine learning regression algorithms. The first approach to expressive drumming generation with deep learning is, to the author's knowledge, the one by Tidemann et. al in 2008 [34]. This model uses Echo State Networks (ESNs, based on RNNs) that generate similar drum patterns to given human drumming patterns, with special emphasis on imitating the groovy aspects of the performance. This system was later incorporated to a virtual agent that also imitated the drummer movements through a motor system [35]. This model was able to efficiently imitate the microtimings, dynamics, and tempo fluctuations of different performers.

A more recent approach is the one by Gillick et al., the GrooVAE model, proposed in 2019 [11]. In their work, a sequence to sequence architecture based on LSTMs is implemented for various tasks: the rendering of expressive performances from a given quantized pattern (humanization), the generation a performance given only microtiming information (tap2drum) and finally, the task of interest to this thesis:

the generation or replacement of instrumental parts of a given pattern (infilling).

2.1.3 The infilling task

As aforementioned, the only model in the literature that addresses the infilling of a drum loop is the one by Gillick et al. [11]. In particular, their system adds the hi-hat part to a drum MIDI performance. Their model is rated as sounding more human than the original performances by 60% of the subjects participating in the evaluation listening tests. The authors suggest that the underlying reason is perhaps the presence of loops played by amateur drummers in the test, which might be performed at a lower level or with some mistaken hits. Given that the model is trained with a dataset consisting of a majority of professional recordings, the model prediction for the hi-hat part might be subjectively better sounding than the (amateur) human performance¹. As Gillick et al. note, this suggests that an infilling model could be used as a “corrective tool that works by resampling parts of an input that have noise or imperfections”. Gillick et al.’s system deals with symbolic musical representations both in the input loop and the output infilling pattern. To the author’s knowledge, the model proposed in this thesis is the first one that tackles the infilling task for drums with an audio input, and with a Transformer architecture.

There exist two additional infilling systems in the literature, yet in the field of piano performances and, as Gillick et al.’s model, in the symbolic domain. Huang et al. [36] introduce a convolutional model that is trained to reconstruct partial scores in an iterative process that is intended to resemble the nonlinear fashion in which humans compose, by iteratively revisiting choices until reaching a final version of the composition. The architecture is based on a convolutional neural network (CNN) in order to explicitly avoid any kind of causal direction of composition, taking advantage of CNNs invariance properties. The model only predicts the pitch of each note

¹However, the questions of whether a performance sounds more human and the question of whether it subjectively sounds better appears to be confounded in the test. Making mistakes when playing is arguably human.

at a particular timestep, and hence, no expressive performance information such as microtiming or dynamics are predicted. In contrast, in the model proposed by Ippolito et al. [12], based on the Transformer architecture, expressive performance information is taken into account by including pitch and velocity to the note representation. In addition, they compare the performance of the Transformer with and without relative attention² [28], and find, in listening experiments, that the relative attention model appears to perform better. However, the sample size is small (8 participants) and no statistical confidence interval is reported, which suggests that this might not be a representative result.

2.2 Deep Learning Architectures for Sequence Modeling

Music is an art of time. In a formal sense, it is constructed by the ordering in time of tones, and more generally, of sounds. The unfolding of music in time also results in a critical role of memory in music perception [37]. In order to teach computational systems how to create music, their architecture must be able to understand its sequential nature. This section provides an overview of a number of architectures that deal with the modeling of sequential data.

2.2.1 Recurrent Neural Networks

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are a family of architectures for processing sequential data [4]. Based on Rumelhart et al. work in 1986 [38], the main idea behind these architectures is that of sharing parameters across the network. RNNs are built by stacking identical hidden units, where each unit outputs an element that is, in turn, the input element of the next hidden layer. The recursion lies in that each

²A variant of the attention mechanism, proposed by Shaw et al. [27], that is able to deal with longer sequences. The attention mechanism will be discussed in detail in Section 2.3.1.

output is a function of the previous members of the output [4]. This is illustrated in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Compact (left) and unrolled (right) representation of a simplified RNN. A corresponds to the hidden unit, x_t is an input at a timestep t , and h_t , the output at that same timestep³.

In the unrolled representation, it can be seen that the information flows through identical units A . These units share the same parameters, which allows them to process the input sequences $(x_i)_{i=0}^n$ of variable length n without having to update the parameters of A if the length n changes. Instead, in order to process an extra item of the sequence, it is only required to stack an extra unit A to the model.

RNNs were one of the first deep learning architectures effectively used for music generation [39]. As exposed in Section 2.1, RNNs have been effectively used for expressive performance generation. However, as occurs with deep networks (i.e., with a large amount of hidden layers), they have difficulty dealing with long-term dependencies due to the vanishing and exploding gradient problem⁴. Moreover, even if the parameters are stable, the network gives exponentially smaller weights to long-term interactions compared to short-term ones. This was early noticed by Hochreiter in 1991 [40], who along with Schmidhuber introduced the Long Short-Term Memory units in 1997 [41] for improving RNNs' ability of dealing with long-

³Image obtained from Christopher Olah's blogpost *Understanding LSTM Networks*, posted on 27/08/2015: <http://colah.github.io/posts/2015-08-Understanding-LSTMs/>. All online resources in this thesis have been last accessed on 31/08/2021.

⁴During the training of a RNN, the unit's parameters are updated by backpropagation. If the model has a large number of layers stacked, this will result in the product of a large number of terms, that will either grow (explode) or diminish (vanish) rapidly. This is known as the vanishing or exploding gradient problem.

term dependencies.

Long Short-Term Memory Networks

LSTMs [41] were proposed in order to deal with long-term dependencies in RNNs by making improvements on the vanishing/exploding gradient problem. LSTMs are based on the idea of storing information for long periods of time and forgetting it when it is no longer necessary. For example, if a sequence is composed by a series of subsequences, the network will learn to accumulate information about a subsequence and then forget about it when it enters a new subsequence. LSTMs are gated RNNs, which means that they have the same inputs and outputs as an ordinary RNN unit, but with extra parameters and gating subunits that control the flow of information of the unit [4]. Another popular gated RNN model is the GRU (gated recurrent unit), though LSTMs are the standard for RNNs [5].

Encoder-decoder sequence-to-sequence architectures

RNNs can map input sequences into vectors of fixed lengths or inversely, map input vectors of fixed lengths to an output sequence. Both arrangements can be combined in order to obtain a sequence-to-sequence architecture used, for example, in machine translation. The encoder in an encoder-decoder architecture can be understood as a mapping between the source domain (e.g., language A) to a ‘common-representation’ (vector of fixed length). The decoder maps this ‘common-representation’ into the target domain (e.g., language B). The ‘common-representation’ vector contains a summary of the input sequence sufficient for the decoder to translate it into the target domain. Variable-length sequence-to-sequence architectures based on RNNs were proposed independently by Cho et al. [42] and Sutskever et al. [43] in 2014. One year later, Bahdanau et al. [44] also introduced the attention mechanism to a RNN-based sequence-to-sequence architecture.

2.2.2 Limitations of Recurrent Neural Networks

Some of the achievements of LSTMs for music generation have been listed in Section 2.1. However, even when LSTMs significantly improve the ability of RNNs to capture long-term dependencies, the vanishing gradient problem still persists if the input sequences are arbitrarily long. This is due to their sequential architecture, since the layer depth can be arbitrarily large (as large as the elements of the input sequence), which in turn, can result in a large number of training steps. While LSTMs improve the ability of vanilla RNNs of capturing longer dependencies, the range of these dependencies is still constrained due to the aforementioned limitations. Some implementations sort this limitation by using a hierarchical approach, processing the same sequences at various levels (e.g., measure-level and then refined at note-level [23]). However, the fundamental problem of the architecture persists. Moreover, sequential computation prevents parallelization within the training examples, which becomes critical at longer sequence lengths [13].

The fact that architectures that generate music need to understand this sequential nature does not imply that the architecture on itself must be sequential. The Transformer, a model that effectively deals with sequences without recurrence and allows for parallelization, will be introduced in next section.

2.3 The Transformer

Inspired by the success of attention mechanisms in visual computing, Vaswani et al. presented the Transformer Architecture in 2017 [13]. The Transformer is trained without recurrence, which prevents it from inheriting the problems of RNNs. Instead, the Transformer is based on the attention mechanism.

2.3.1 The Attention Mechanism

The attention mechanism computes the similarity between elements of the model’s input (self-attention) or between the elements of the input and the output (cross-attention). The intuition behind attention can be understood in the context of machine translation. In order to translate the word *head* in the sentence “Louisa is the head of the department.” to Spanish (“Louisa es la jefa del departamento.”), the context needs to be taken into account. By the word *department*, it can be inferred that the word *head* refers to director (*jefa/jefe*) and not to the skull (*cabeza*). On the other hand, Louisa is a female name, and in consequence, the translation would be *jefa* instead of *jefe*. The attention mechanism would give more weight to the words *department* and *Louisa* than to the rest of the words in the sentence for the purpose of translating the word *head*. In short, the attention mechanism is a weighted average of the elements in a sequence that informs the architecture on which words to focus when translating a particular word.

Computing attention

Each element in the input sequence is represented by a vector. This vector representation can be obtained by embedding techniques or tokenization. For each of these input vector \mathbf{x}_i , three further representations⁵ are obtained: the query \mathbf{q}_i , the key \mathbf{k}_i and the value \mathbf{v}_i . The query and key vectors are of dimension d_k and the values vectors are of dimension d_v . These representations can be understood as projections of the same vector onto three different spaces. In order to make use of matrix operations, all the input vectors are joint in a matrix \mathbf{X} , and the projected vectors are hence also joined as the matrices \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{V} for the query-, key-, and

⁵The use of database terminology is not casual: the computation of attention resembles a query-search in a database. In standard databases, a value is retrieved when its key is identical to the query. In the attention, there is no one-to-one correspondence between keys and query, so the ‘database’ returns a weighted average of the values by computing the similarity between query and keys.

value-spaces respectively.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{Q} &= \mathbf{W}_Q^T \mathbf{X} \\ \mathbf{K} &= \mathbf{W}_K^T \mathbf{X} \\ \mathbf{V} &= \mathbf{W}_V^T \mathbf{X}\end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{W}_i is the projection matrix from the space in which the input matrix \mathbf{X} lives to the space i . These projection matrices are learnt during the training process.

The attention matrix for each input matrix \mathbf{X} is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right) \mathbf{V} \quad (2.1)$$

This is referred to as Scaled Dot-Product Attention by Vaswani et al. [13]. It makes use of the dot-product as a similarity measure between two vectors. The reason for the scaling is due to the natural scaling of the dot-product with the dimension size d_k of \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{K} . The computation is illustrated in Figure 2.3. After computing the scaled dot product, the resulting similarity matrix can be passed through a masking layer that blocks certain elements of the sequence so that they are not taken into account (i.e., are given weight zero) in the computation of the attention values. The usage of masking will be described in next subsection in the context of the encoder and decoder of the Transformer Architecture.

When the query, key and value matrices result from projecting the same input matrix, the attention mechanism is known as self-attention. If the query matrix results from the projection of the output matrix, this mechanism is known as cross-attention. Both self- and cross-attention modules are included in the Transformer architecture.

Figure 2.3: Scaled-dot product attention. Figure by Vaswani et al. [13].

Multi-head attention

Instead of calculating the scaled-dot product attention for each set of matrices \mathbf{V} , \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{Q} , in the Transformer Architecture, those matrices are divided in submatrices \mathbf{V}_h , \mathbf{K}_h and \mathbf{Q}_h , where the subindex ‘h’ refers to *head*. The attention values are computed in parallel for each head and the resulting values are concatenated. This is known as multi-head attention (Figure 2.4). The subdivision of matrices is done across the embedding dimension: each input vector is divided in subvectors of equal length, and each matrix of subvectors is passed through an attention head in parallel. Before feeding the submatrices into the attention heads, the submatrices are passed through a linear layer that mixes information between the sub-divisions or heads.

2.3.2 The Transformer Architecture

Attention mechanisms had been previously used for sequence modeling in conjunction with RNNs [44] and in the context of computer vision, with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [45]. However, the Transformer architecture is the first transduction model based entirely on attention mechanisms [13].

The Transformer is an encoder-decoder architecture. The encoder generates a representation of the input sequence, which is passed to the decoder, that translates

Figure 2.4: The Multi-head Attention module. Figure by Vaswani et al. [13].

Figure 2.5: The Transformer Architecture. Figure by Vaswani et al. [13].

this representation into an output sequence. Figure 2.5 illustrates the Transformer Architecture. The left block corresponds to the encoder while the right block corresponds to the decoder.

Encoder

The encoder consists of N identical blocks stacked, where each block contains a multi-head module and a feed-forward module. After each module, there are residual connections to keep the module's input representation across layers. This is relevant since in the multi-head attention module there is a mix of information between heads (linear layers). After adding the inputs to the output of each module, layer normalization [46] is performed. The feed-forward module maps the inputs into a larger dimension, and afterwards maps this expanded representation into the same dimension as the input. This feed-forward expansion is applied equally to all elements in the sequence.

Decoder

The decoder has a similar structure to the encoder, consisting as well in a stack of N identical blocks that contain multi-head attention and feed-forward modules. However, in contrast to the encoder, the decoder receives as input the last output of the full architecture. In this sense, the architecture makes also use of the context in the target domain through the first masked multi-head attention module. The second multi-head attention module performs a cross-attention operation using the query from the last outputted element (the input in the encoder) and the keys and values received from the encoder. The resulting values are passed to a feed-forward expansion, as occurs in the encoder. Again, the inputs of each module are added to their outputs in order to maintain the original information through the layers. Layer normalization [46] is also performed.

Training parallelization

During inference, the decoder receives the output of the encoder and also its own last output (the model's output from the last timestep). There is strictly recursion during inference in the Transformer Architecture. However, during training, instead of feeding the last output recursively (i.e., predicting one step at a time), the ground truth output sequence is fed all at once so that the training can be done completely in parallel.

The mask in the first multi-head attention layer in the decoder module prevents each item of the shifted output sequence to look at items in the future timesteps. This simulates the recurrence process in the inference, where the information of future timesteps is unknown, but without having to train the model recursively, which makes the Transformer much faster in training than its recursive counterparts.

This implies training the model in a teacher forcing fashion, where instead of using the model's prediction at timestep t as input to the model at timestep $t + 1$, the ground truth at timestep t is used. This could imply a loss in generalization of the model [4], but this is compensated by adding dropout connections [47] both in the encoder and decoder layers. Dropout connections consist in a random drop of connections during the training, which effectively results in that the model does not know all the information during the training, which improves generalization. The dropouts are applied at the end of each sublayer before adding the inputs and normalizing, as well as to the sum of the embedding and positional encoding, which will be described in next section.

Positional Encoding

In the Transformer architecture, all elements of the sequence can be passed at once as inputs. As seen in Section 2.3.1, the input vectors are passed as a single matrix. However, permuting the columns of the input matrix \mathbf{X} does not have any influ-

ence on the attention matrix calculation (Equation 2.1) apart from permuting its columns. This might seem inconsistent with the idea of working with sequences. For this reason, the position of the element sequence is encoded in the same vector by adding a positional-encoding vector. The positional encodings used in the Transformer architecture correspond to sinusoidal functions. Using periodic functions is not arbitrary, since they encode both the absolute position of the item in the sequence as well as the relative position between items in the sequence. The performance of the original Transformer [13], was improved by Shaw et al. [27] on machine translation tasks by using a relative positional encoding that is able to capture relative relations between the elements in the sequence. However, this is impractical for long compositions due to the quadratic memory cost [28].

Masking

Masking items in both the input and shifted output sequence prevents the model from taking into account information we do not want the model to consider. In the masked multi-head attention layer in the decoder (Figure 2.5), the masking prevents each item in the output sequence to take into account the items of further steps in their attention calculation. Masking is also of relevance when feeding the model with sequences of different length. A maximum sequence length is imposed, and sequences with a shorter length are added zero input vectors at the end (padding). However, since these padding vectors do not contain relevant information, they are masked in the attention modules. This allows using the same architecture for sequences of different length.

Another usage of attention consists in blocking certain elements in the sequence. In the BERT [48] pretrained Transformer encoder, Devlin et al. show that training a Transformer encoder based language model by predicting some masked inputs (also known as the Cloze task) or predicting if two sentences are consecutive significantly improves the language understanding of a model.

Memory limitations

Although ideally the Transformer can capture arbitrarily long-term dependencies in a sequence (global attention), this implies feeding the full sequence in parallel to the Transformer. The memory requirement grows quadratically with the sequence length, which limits the size of the input sequence in terms of memory requirements. The memory constraints impose a maximum batch⁶ size across for which dependencies can be effectively captured, but information is not shared across batches. The Transformer-XL model [30], allows for sequences of different length (without imposing a maximum length condition, as aforementioned) by using ‘cached’ batches, i.e., each batch is able to access information from previous batches, giving extra context to the batch prediction. Another relevant approach is the one used in the Music Transformer [28]. The relative attention Transformer proposed by Shaw et al. [27], has a complexity of $O(L^2D)$ where L is the maximum sequence length and D is the embedding size. Huang et al. reduce this memory requirement to $O(LD)$ by implementing a ‘relative global attention’. This allows for generating music with long-term structure, since the model can attend to longer sequences for a lesser memory cost.

Another recent approach is the one used in the Perceiver Transformer [49], in which the complexity is drastically reduced by using attention bottlenecks (the query has a much lower dimension than the keys and values, so the attention matrices scale by $M \times N$ where $M \gg N$). This model exploits the lack of assumptions done in the Transformer architecture with respect to its inputs (in contrast to CNNs, which pass filters over images, or the Vision Transformer [16], that subdivides an image in patches) and achieves state of the art accuracies for tasks in audio, video, pointclouds and images.

⁶In deep learning, the batch size is the number of training examples a model sees before back-propagation, i.e., before updating its parameters.

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this thesis, we develop the Transformer Groove Infilling model, a deep learning model based on the Transformer architecture that performs the infilling task. We trained several instances of the model on the following infilling subtasks:

- **Infilling Closed Hi-Hats:** the model predicts the closed hi-hat part of an input audio drum loop that lacks the closed hi-hat part.
- **Infilling Kicks And Snares:** the model predicts the kick and/or snare for an input audio drum loop that lacks the kick and/or snare part.
- **Infilling Random:** the model predicts events (hits) for an incomplete input audio drum loop.

The subtask names given here will be used in the following sections to refer to the experiments that involved training the Transformer Groove Infilling model to perform such tasks. In this chapter, we describe the dataset, data representation and processing strategy, model architecture, loss function, and the specific details

of each experiment. All the code is documented and available at¹:

<https://github.com/pelinski/TransformerGrooveInfilling>

3.1 Dataset

The datasets used for training the Transformer Groove Infilling model for each infilling subtask have been obtained after processing the Groove MIDI Dataset (GMD)² [11]. The GMD consists of 13.6 hours, 1.150 MIDI files and 22.000 measures of drumming. 10 drummers participated in the recordings, 5 professionals and 5 amateurs, with an 80% of the dataset coming from the professionals' performances. The performances were played along with a metronome set to a specific tempo by the performer. The metronome allows to quantize the offsets of every hit with respect to each beat sub-division, but in turn, it might limit the tempo dynamics by constraining the performance to a fixed tempo. The performances selected for this work are in 4/4, which are the majority, and are annotated by drummer id and the genre according to the drummer's criteria, which results in 18 different genres. Table 3.1 shows the total number of items as well as the percentage of items belonging to each genre in each dataset split³. As it can be observed, there are strong imbalances across genres: 72% of the training examples are tagged as rock, latin, jazz, or funk.

The drum performances are recorded in MIDI format on an electronic drum kit, the Roland TD-11. This drum kit contains 22 different MIDI pitches (Table 3.2) and some of them correspond to different parts or ways of playing the same instrument

¹At the time of submission, some of the libraries mentioned in the following sections have not been yet made public. For the time being, a standalone version of the the Transformer Groove Infilling including the current version of those libraries can be downloaded here: <https://zenodo.org/record/5347908>.

²Available at <https://magenta.tensorflow.org/datasets/groove>.

³The dataset splits are also provided by the GMD authors [11].

Genre	Train	Test	Validation
afrobeat	4.8 %	3.8 %	5.8 %
afrocuban	4.7 %	–	–
blues	0.5 %	–	–
country	0.7 %	–	–
dance	3.4 %	–	–
funk	9.7 %	23.7 %	17.8 %
gospel	–	–	3.4 %
highlife	0.3 %	4.6 %	–
hiphop	4.4 %	5.4 %	0.7 %
jazz	12.8 %	3.1 %	4.5 %
latin	17.0 %	14.6 %	23.3 %
middleeastern	0.7 %	–	–
neworleans	4.4 %	–	–
pop	0.7 %	2.9 %	6.6 %
punk	0.6 %	2.8 %	6.0 %
reggae	1.0 %	5.8 %	–
rock	32.5 %	18.0 %	32.0 %
soul	1.7 %	15.2 %	–
Total number of 2-bar loops	16266	2054	2021

Table 3.1: Genre distribution and total number of items in GMD splits.

(e.g., snare head or rim). This is a large vocabulary and with strong imbalances in terms of instrument hit occurrence, which is common among drum datasets [50], since some instruments, due to their ‘role’ in the drum kit and the drum vocabulary, are played more often than others (e.g., snares vs. crash).

The initial 22-voice vocabulary⁴ of the Roland TD-11 has been reduced by the authors of the dataset [11] to a 9-voice vocabulary. The correspondence between both vocabularies can be found in Table 3.2. The 9-voice vocabulary presented in Table 3.2 provides a good compromise between a reasonable task complexity and a large enough vocabulary, larger than the 3-voice (kicks, snares and hi-hats) vocabulary used in most automatic drum transcription systems. Moreover, we expect the model to have a sufficient degree of robustness when presented with different drum

⁴By voice we refer to instrument in the drum kit and by vocabulary to the number of instruments present in the drum kit.

kits (i.e., different types of soundfonts, acoustic as well as electronic), which could be compromised by an overly extensive vocabulary.

MIDI Pitch	Roland TD-11 vocabulary	9-voice vocabulary (MIDI pitch)	Hit percentage
36	Kick	Kick (36)	19.6 %
38	Snare (Head)	Snare (38)	30.0 %
40	Snare (Rim)		
37	Snare X-Stick		
45	Tom 2	Low Tom (45)	3.6 %
43	Tom 3 (Head)		
58	Tom 3 (Rim)		
48	Tom 1	Mid Tom (48)	3.2 %
47	Tom 2 (Rim)		
50	Tom 1 (Rim)	High Tom (50)	0.3 %
46	HH Open (Bow)	Open Hi-Hat (46)	3.2 %
26	HH Open (Edge)		
42	HH Closed (Bow)	Closed Hi-Hat (42)	26.5 %
22	HH Closed (Edge)		
44	HH Pedal		
49	Crash 1 (Bow)	Crash (49)	2.0 %
55	Crash 1 (Edge)		
57	Crash 2 (Bow)		
52	Crash 2 (Edge)		
51	Ride (Bow)	Ride (51)	11.5 %
59	Ride (Edge)		
53	Ride (Bell)		
Total number of hits			448783

Table 3.2: Groove Midi Dataset (GMD) voice mapping and percentage of hits for each instrument over total hit count. Mapping and data extracted from [11].

Although MIDI is a limited protocol in terms of expression [51], in the case of drums, since there are no continuous changes in a note, the format is adequate for capturing velocity and onsets information. However, as it has been discussed, the variety of forms in which an instrument of the drum kit can be played is lost.

The GMD is used both for training (test split), model hyperparameter tuning (test split) and evaluation (validation split), which is a very extended procedure but not the best for objective system evaluation, since there exists the possibility that the model “is learning the dataset and not the task”⁵. The dataset processing pipeline used to generate the model training inputs and ground truths will be described in the next sections.

3.2 Data representation

As illustrated in Figure 3.1, the Transformer Groove Infilling model receives a 2-bar input audio loop and outputs a symbolic representation of the ‘infilled’ loop parts (e.g., a missing instrument in the input pattern). The numerical representation of the input audio corresponds to a reduced representation (discussed in Section 3.2.2) of an onset spectrogram, both in the time and audio domain. The output symbolic representation (discussed in Section 3.2.3) captures hit, velocity and offsets information for each instrument in the instrument vocabulary (in this case, 9 voices), and it is easily convertible to MIDI format and synthesized if given a soundfont⁶. A scheme showing the data representation terminology can be found in Figure 3.2. Before introducing each data representation, we discuss the importance of using a direct representation instead of a tokenized representation, usual in language models such as the Transformer architecture.

3.2.1 Tokenized representations vs. direct representations

Deep learning models used for music generation tasks are commonly first conceived in the field of natural language processing (NLP), as is the case of the Transformer

⁵This was an observation made by Santiago Ontañón in his talk *Pushing the Limits of Transformer Models* at the IIIA Seminars (06/07/21).

⁶A soundfont is a collection of drum instrument sounds used for synthesizing each instrument in the drum kit. They can be easily used for synthesizing MIDI patterns and can be found online without difficulty.

Figure 3.1: Transformer Groove Infilling model overview. The model receives an input audio drum loop and outputs a symbolic representation of the infilled events.

Figure 3.2: Transformer Groove Infilling data representation overview. The input audio drum loop is converted into a direct representation, the multiband synthesized onsets (MSO, Section 3.2.2), and the output data format corresponds to a symbolic representation (HVO, Section 3.2.3), that can be easily transformed to MIDI and synthesized with a soundfont.

architecture. Since computers can not understand words directly, NLP models assign a discrete token (a serial code) to each different word. Then, tokens are mapped to a continuous space in a distributional semantic fashion, i.e., words that are close have similar meanings. This process of assigning a discrete variable (the token) a continuous representation is known as embedding. The embedding is learned by the model during training.

The use of tokenization has extended to music generation due to the influence of NLP. However, musical events are usually agnostic and have no meaning by themselves but in context, and hence, learning an embedded representation of the events in terms of similarity is perhaps not be the most straightforward approach. Musical events can also be directly numerically described, and moreover, using audio signal processing techniques, as is the case of this thesis, a numerical representation can

be obtained directly from the audio. Moreover, the model does not have to learn an embedded representation from an arbitrary token, and the internal representations learnt in the model might be easier to learn since in direct numerical representations, the similarity is explicit (i.e., the offset values -0.1 and -0.2 are closer than the offset values of -0.1 and 0.3).

The infilling system by Ippolito et al. [12] uses a tokenized representation (the Note-Tuple [52]), whereas both Huang et al.’s [36] and Gillick et al.’s [11] use a direct representation of the input score. However, either of them obtains this representation directly from the audio.

3.2.2 Input data representation: Multiband Synthesized Onsets (MSO)

As already mentioned, our Transformer Infilling Model receives an input audio loop. A straightforward numerical representation of an audio signal could be a spectral transform such as the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) or a Mel spectrogram. However, as discussed in Section 2.3.2, the memory requirement of a Transformer architecture grows quadratically with the input sequence length. Interpreting a spectrogram as an input sequence results in a sequence of equal length to the number of timeframes, which will generally be much larger than a musical sequence quantized by tempo subdivisions (e.g., 32 timesteps for 2 bars with 16 subdivisions each). Moreover, the motivation behind using sequence modeling architectures such as the Transformer architecture for music generation lies in taking advantage of the sequential nature of music⁷.

⁷If trained with sufficient resources, the Transformer architecture can also learn to interpret spectrograms. The Audio Spectrogram Transformer (AST), proposed recently by Gong et al. [17], achieves state-of-the-art results on audio classification benchmarks. The task of audio classification is of high complexity and can not benefit from sequentiality as in musical-related tasks. In this case, it is reasonable to use all the available information in the spectrogram. However, training a Transformer for such complex task is computationally expensive: the strategy followed by Gong et al. consists in make use of transfer learning from the Vision Transformer (ViT) [16, 53], pretrained on the ImageNet dataset (with 1.3M images) [54].

Benefiting from the sequential nature of music means, in this context, to obtain a reduced symbolic representation of the input audio in both time and frequency domain, that contains enough frequency and time information to perform the desired task (infilling) without being too memory expensive. Since the input audio comprises exclusively drum sounds, the reduced representation we are seeking should contain fine onset information. A reasonable approach could be to obtain the transcription (or, in other words, symbolic representation) of the input audio drum loop. However, Audio Drum Transcription (ADT) also presents several difficulties. The unpitched and highly transient nature of drums makes algorithms for Automatic Music Transcription tailored for pitched instruments, such as those based on harmonic structure, unsuitable for drum transcription [55]. Moreover, there is a strong overlap between instruments of the drum kit in both time and frequency, since generally instruments are played simultaneously and their spectra is noisy. Finally, the infilling task consists in suggesting parts that work well with the input sequence, and thus, the transcription of the sequence might not be strictly necessary, and a simpler reduced representation might be more effective.

ADT systems themselves deal with obtaining a reduced representation (in this case, a symbolic representation) of an audio signal, so their design strategies are of interest here. There are different trends in ADT research⁸, including feature representation (such as spectral transforms), event segmentation, or the obtainment of activation functions [55]. Here, we combine these three approaches drawing from the onset spectrogram used as input feature in the ADT system proposed by Cartwright et al. [50]⁹. We named the resulting representation Multiband Synthesized Onsets

⁸A comprehensive review on ADT systems can be found in [55].

⁹During the course of the thesis, other options were informally explored, such as Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) or reduced Mel spectrograms. However, visualizations of such reduced representations did not seem easily interpretable. Moreover, in the case of NMF, a suitable number of components needs to be chosen, which is not evident in the case of drum audio loops in which generally not all instruments of the drum kit are present.

(MSO)¹⁰.

MSO calculation

The following three steps are used to derive the MSO representation for the input audio drum loops.

- (1) **Differential spectrogram**¹¹ In a first stage, the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) is computed using the librosa¹² [56] implementation. Then, the spectrogram resulting from the dot product of the STFT with a triangular filterbank with center frequencies logarithmically spaced is obtained¹³. An example of the resulting spectrogram is shown in Figure 3.3. Then, the difference between each frame and the previous 22 frames is computed in order to obtain a differential spectrogram (i.e. the moving mean is subtracted). The spectrogram is then half-wave rectified, logarithmically scaled and clipped. The resulting differential spectrogram is shown in Figure 3.4, and the parameters used for the STFT calculation as well as the triangular filterbank definition can be found in Table 3.3.
- (2) **Frequency resolution reduction** Subsequently, we reduce the number of frequency bins to 8 bands. The center frequencies of these bands have been obtained from the work by Herrera et al. [58], where they determine the frequency bands that perform well for drum kit instrument classification. In order to reduce the initial frequency bins to these 8 bands, we select the high-

¹⁰The MSO implementation, coded by the author, is part of the HVO Sequence library, authored by Behzad Haki: https://github.com/behzadhaki/hvo_sequence.

¹¹The code for calculating the differential spectrogram has been adapted from Cartwright and Bello [50]. In their work, they use the differential spectrogram as an input feature for an ADT system.

¹²<https://librosa.org/>.

¹³This resembles a Constant-Q transform [57], which is similar to the STFT but with a constant number of bins per octave instead of a constant frequency difference between bins. This results in a more musically meaningful transform. However, here, instead of calculating the constant Q-Transform directly, the STFT is calculated and then the frequency bins are passed through the triangular filter, resulting in a logarithmically scaling of the STFT (logf-STFT).

Figure 3.3: Resulting spectrogram after multiplying the STFT with a triangular filter-bank with frequencies logarithmically scaled and finally converting the energy values to dB.

Figure 3.4: Differential spectrogram obtained after computing the difference between each frame in the spectrogram and the mean of the 22 previous frames.

Domain	Parameter	Value
STFT	FFT size	1024
	Window size	1024
	Window type	Hamm
	Hop size	441
Triangular Filterbank	Number of bins per octave	16
	Number of octaves	9
	Minimum frequency (Hz)	40

Table 3.3: MSO calculation parameters.

Figure 3.5: Differential spectrogram with frequencies reduced to 8 bands. The value for each band is selected by taking the maximum value in the band in the differential spectrogram from Figure 3.4

est onset spectrogram value for each band and timeframe. An example of the resulting frequency-reduced differential spectrogram is presented in Figure 3.5.

- (3) **Time resolution reduction** Next, we treat each band in the frequency-reduced differential spectrogram as an onset strength envelope and pass it through the librosa [56] onset detection function. This function returns the timeframes at which the hit onsets occur. Since all our input loops have a 2-bar measure, we split each bar into 16 divisions, resulting in a 32 timestep grid for each 2-bar loop. We create an offset¹⁴ matrix and an onset strength matrix, each with 32 columns (timesteps), and 8 rows (bands). Both matrices have

¹⁴Hereon offset will refer to the microtiming deviation of a hit to the closest timestep.

the non-zero values at the same positions, since a non-zero value indicates that there is a hit happening at that particular timestep and frequency band. The values in the offset matrix correspond to the difference between the timeframe at which a hit onset occurs and its nearest timestep (column) in the grid. The values in the onset strength matrix correspond to the differential spectrogram value at the timeframe at which the onset occurs. The stacking of these two matrices results in the MSO matrix, which has a shape of 16×32 .

s_1	0	0.54	0	0.85
s_2	0.55	0	0.17	0
s_3	0.46	0	0.38	0
o_1	0	0.09	0	0.36
o_2	-0.30	0	-0.25	0
o_3	-0.30	0	-0.30	0

Table 3.4: Example of MSO for 3 frequency bands, 1 bar at 4-4. Each column corresponds to a timestep. Rows 1 to 3 correspond to the onset strength (s_i) value, and rows 4 to 6 corresponds to the offsets (o_i) of each hit with respect to the corresponding timestep (column).

3.2.3 Output data representation: HVO

The Transformer Groove Infilling model outputs a symbolic representation of the infilled pattern. That representation is named HVO, after the hit (H), velocity (V), and offset (O) information it comprises of each percussive event in the infilled pattern, and is similar to the one used in the work by Gillick et al. [11]. Due to the instant and percussive nature of the drum performances, the release information (i.e., ‘note-off’ MIDI messages) is disregarded.

Each sequence is represented by three stacked $T \times M$ matrices, where T corresponds to the number of timesteps, in this case, 32 (2 bars with 16 sub-divisions each), and M corresponds to the number of instruments, in this case, 9. The three matrices are defined as follows:

- **Hits:** Binary-valued matrix that indicates the presence (1) or absence (0) of a drum hit.
- **Velocity:** Continuous-valued matrix, with values in range $[0, 1]$ that contains the hit velocity information.
- **Offsets:** Continuous-valued matrix with values in range $[-0.5, 0.5]$ that indicates the hit’s deviation or offset from the nearest timestep (in this case, the nearest 16th note).

h_1	0	1	0	1
h_2	0	0	1	0
h_3	1	0	1	0
v_1	0	0.42	0	0.58
v_2	0	0	0.84	0
v_3	0.67	0	0.53	0
o_1	0	-0.32	0	-0.10
o_2	0	0	0.12	0
o_3	0.21	0	-0.09	0

Table 3.5: Example of HVO for 3 instruments, 1 bar at 4-4. Each column corresponds to a timestep. Rows 1 to 3 correspond to the hits (h_i), rows 4 to 6 correspond to the velocities (v_i) and rows 7 to 9 correspond to the offsets (o_i) of each hit with respect to the corresponding timestep (column).

This results in a HVO matrix of dimension 32×27 . An example of an HVO representation for 3 instruments and 4 timesteps can be found in Table 3.5. In the next section, we will describe how we obtain both input and output data representations from the Groove Midi Dataset (GMD).

3.2.4 Data processing pipeline

The items in the GMD are in MIDI format and correspond to 2-bar performances, so we need to process those items in order to obtain the input audio drum loops corresponding to each experiment (e.g., the audio without the closed hi-hat part) and the corresponding ground truths (e.g., the symbolic representation of the closed

h_1	0	1	0	1
h_2	0	0	0	0
h_3	1	0	1	0
v_1	0	0.42	0	0.58
v_2	0	0	0	0
v_3	0.67	0	0.53	0
o_1	0	-0.32	0	-0.10
o_2	0	0	0	0
o_3	0.21	0	-0.09	0

Table 3.6: Example of the input loop HVO, obtained after setting to 0 voice 2. We compute the input MSO from the audio loop synthesized from this HVO.

h_1	0	0	0	0
h_2	0	0	1	0
h_3	0	0	0	0
v_1	0	0	0	0
v_2	0	0	0.84	0
v_3	0	0	0	0
o_1	0	0	0	0
o_2	0	0	0.12	0
o_3	0	0	0	0

Table 3.7: Example of ground truth HVO, where all voices except the 2 are set to 0.

hi-hat part). First, we obtain the HVO representation for each input loop¹⁵. In the HVO example of Table 3.5, we have three instruments. In the case of the task of infilling an instrument, for example, voice 2, we would set the corresponding rows (i.e., h_2, v_2, o_2) to 0, as in Table 3.6, synthesize the pattern at sampling frequency 44100 Hz with a particular soundfont and obtain its corresponding MSO. In order to generate the ground truth, we do the inverse operation by removing all voices except voice 2, as in Table 3.7. Since the ground truths are in HVO format, this needs no further processing. The process for infilling events independently of the drum kit instrument is equivalent, but instead of removing full rows, only certain positions in the matrix are removed.

The details on the dataset processing for each particular experiment will be given in Section 3.5. First, we introduce the architecture of the Transformer Groove Infilling model.

¹⁵All the HVO manipulation is integrated on the HVO Sequence library, authored by Behzad Haki: https://github.com/behzadhaki/hvo_sequence.

3.3 Transformer Groove Infilling Model Architecture

The Transformer Groove Infilling model only uses the Transformer Encoder block from the original Vaswani et al.’s [13] Transformer encoder-decoder architecture. As exposed in Section 2.3, the Transformer encoder maps the input sequence to a continuous representation, whereas the decoder maps this continuous representation to the output sequence, one element at a time. During inference, the decoder makes use of auto-regression to provide the output sequence not only with the information coming from the encoder, but also using information from the previous predicted steps of the output sequence (cross-attention). Here, we assume that only with the encoder the infilling task can be achieved. This way, we dispose of recurrence during inference, which results in faster generation¹⁶. Moreover, in the task of machine translation, where the Transformer was initially proposed, the grammatical concordance in the output sequence is crucial. While the context is crucial also for generating a hit in a drum pattern (arguably, musical events do not make sense without context), the ‘grammatical concordance’ of a drum pattern might not be as rigid as in natural language. Following this intuition, we assume that the Transformer encode is sufficient to perform the infilling task.

In our approach¹⁷, we use the original input block (with a linear layer and the positional encoder), that feeds the processed inputs to the Transformer encoder. Similar to the original Transformer Architecture, we stack a number of encoder blocks. We add a tailored output block after the encoder layers that contains a linear layer.

¹⁶In practice, this also results in faster training times since after a number of epochs, typically 10, we perform an evaluation on the train and evaluation sets in which we use inference.

¹⁷The model code has been written collaboratively with Marina Nieto and Behzad Haki in PyTorch 1.8.1 [59] at <https://github.com/behzadhaki/BaseGrooveTransformers>.

The input linear layer maps the dimension of each element of the input sequence to the model embedding dimension. In our case, the input dimension is the MSO dimension for each timestep, i.e., 16: 8 onset strength values and 8 offset values. The model embedding dimension has been determined for each particular model experiment with hyperparameter tuning, which will be discussed in Section 3.4.3. The output linear layer maps each item of the sequence from the model embedding dimension to the output dimension, the HVO size of each item in the sequence: 27, as noted in Section 3.2.3.

3.4 Training

There are two main paradigms in machine learning¹⁸: supervised and unsupervised learning. The difference between both is the kind of experience that they are allowed to have during training [4]. Roughly, unsupervised learning algorithms learn patterns in the dataset. Some unsupervised learning algorithms involve learning the probability distribution of features in the dataset or clustering dataset items by similarity. In contrast, in supervised learning, each item in the dataset has a target associated with it, and the algorithm tries to predict the target accurately.

The Transformer Groove Infilling model learns in a supervised fashion, i.e., the dataset contains the input items as well as the expected outputs, (in the deep learning jargon, ground truths). When the training starts, the Transformer parameters¹⁹ are initialized randomly. The Transformer then receives a batch of input items of the dataset and predicts the output items (in this case, infilled patterns) for each item in the batch. In supervised learning, we compare the predictions with the ground truths and update the model parameters accordingly. We obtain a measure of how different the prediction from the ground truth is (i.e., the loss

¹⁸Currently, a third paradigm is gaining importance: reinforcement learning. These algorithms learn from interacting with an environment [4].

¹⁹Not to be mistaken with the hyperparameters, which are not learned by the model and are determined before training.

value, calculated with the loss function), and this information is passed back to the model to readjust the parameters to minimize the difference between prediction and ground truth (mathematically, to minimize the loss). This process is repeated for each batch of items in the dataset until the model has seen the full dataset. At this point, it is said that the model has been trained for an epoch. The number of epochs a model needs to learn to perform the task will vary depending on the task and the hyperparameters²⁰.

The loss function determines directly how the model learns to perform the task, and for this reason, its definition is crucial.

3.4.1 Loss function

Since the model outputs are HVO matrices, in practice, the loss function compares two matrices of dimension timesteps \times (hits, velocity, offsets). We define the loss \mathcal{L} for each instrument i at timestep j as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{i,j} = \Theta(w)_{i,j} (\mathcal{L}_{hi,j} + \mathcal{L}_{vi,j} + \mathcal{L}_{oi,j}) \quad (3.1)$$

where \mathcal{L}_h corresponds to the hit loss, \mathcal{L}_v to the velocity loss, \mathcal{L}_o corresponds to the offset loss.

The hit loss \mathcal{L}_h corresponds to the Binary Cross Entropy (BCE), defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{hi,j} = -h_{i,j} \ln(\hat{h}_{i,j}) - (1 - h_{i,j}) \ln(1 - \hat{h}_{i,j}) \quad (3.2)$$

where $h_{i,j}$ corresponds to the predicted hit for a timestep i and instrument j . And $\hat{h}_{i,j}$ corresponds to the corresponding predicted hit. The BCE is usually used for

²⁰As mentioned in the previous footnote, the hyperparameters are fixed parameters that not learnt by the model during training. The notion of hyperparameter and its implications is further explained in Section 3.4.3

multilabel classification problems, which is the case if we interpret 1 as class ‘hit happening’ and 0 as class ‘hit not happening’. If we assigned 0 to ‘hit happening’ and 1 to ‘hit not happening’, the problem would be equivalent, so we need a metric that is able to penalize misclassification and has this symmetric property. In contrast, in the case of the velocities and offsets, we are dealing with continuous values ($v \in [0, 1]$, $o \in [-0.5, 0.5]$) that do not represent the belonging to a class but a magnitude. For this reason, we calculate the loss in the velocities and offsets as the Mean Square Error (MSE). The MSE is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{xi,j} = (x_{i,j} - \hat{x}_{i,j})^2 \quad (3.3)$$

where x is v or o and \hat{x} is \hat{v} or \hat{o} .

In equation 3.1, we include a parameter $\Theta(w)_{i,j}$ that weights the sum of the hit, velocity and offset loss. This parameter is defined as:

$$\Theta(w)_{i,j} = \begin{cases} w & \text{if } h_{i,j} = 0. \\ 1 & \text{if } h_{i,j} = 1. \end{cases} \quad (3.4)$$

where w is a hyperparameter and $w \in (0, 1]$. This weighting factor was included in order to give more importance for the model to learn the positions where hits occur (1) in contrast to learning the positions where hits do not occur (which are the majority). With this, we are trying to prevent the model from predicting empty scores and still obtaining low losses. We implemented this after a series of informal experiments, in which we also tried to normalize the losses after the first batch in training (i.e., the first loss was always 3, the sum of unit loss of hit, velocity and offset). However, this normalization resulted in the models learning to predict only empty scores. An interpretation of this behavior could be that it is easier for the model to learn first the hits and then the offsets and velocities, so trying to force

the model to give the same importance as hits to offsets and velocities would result in zero predictions. For this reason, we try to penalize the empty predictions with the parameter $\Theta(w)_{i,j}$, in which w is a hyperparameter.

3.4.2 Experiment tracking and reproducibility

We implemented W&B²¹ [60] in the training pipeline for the purpose of live experiment tracking. W&B provides an online visualization tool of graphs and media (audios, scores, pattern heatmaps) that allows pushing results at each step of the training process, as well as saving the model periodically. A subjective evaluation of the evolution of the model predictions during training might also be informative in terms of interpreting how the model is learning to perform the task. Additionally, W&B offers the sweep tool for hyperparameter tuning, which will be discussed in next section.

This serves not only the purpose of user-friendly navigation of results as well as a way of live tracking the experiments but also the purpose of reproducibility and openness. Reproducibility is crucial to ensure the validity of the experimental results, yet in machine learning, reproducing another author’s paper is usually hard due to several difficulties such as the lack of access to the dataset, code, non-reported hyperparameters, and the selective report of results [61]. In order to make our results as ‘reproducible-friendly’ as possible, along with the training procedure, we release our code, dataset, and python environment specifications used in this thesis’ experiments.

3.4.3 Hyperparameter tuning

In machine learning, hyperparameters refer to the parameters of the learning algorithm that are not learned and need to be determined externally. Those hy-

²¹<https://wandb.ai/>.

hyperparameters determine the performance of the model in terms of training time, memory cost, and learning ability [4]. For this reason, we undergo a hyperparameter tuning stage before training our models. In order to determine a hyperparameter combination with an optimal performance²², we train the same model with random hyperparameter combinations for a reduced number of epochs (100) and select the one giving the best results. For this purpose, we used the random sweep tool in W&B²³

The hyperparameters of the model are defined in Table 3.8.

Domain	Hyperparameter
Transformer Architecture	Model embedding dimension
	Number of encoder blocks
	Number of multi-head attention heads
	Feedforward layer dimension
	Dropout value
Training	Learning rate
	Batch size
	Hit loss penalty (w)
	Optimizer

Table 3.8: Transformer Groove Infilling model hyperparameters.

Since the hit loss penalty w is a hyperparameter, the losses can not be compared across experiments. In order to determine the best hyperparameters, we compare the metrics in the test split of the dataset, consisting of examples not seen by the model during training.

3.5 Experiments

As it has been introduced at the start of the chapter, during the course of this thesis, three different experiments were conducted. The first two of them (Infilling Closed

²²Strictly speaking, finding the hyperparameter combination with an optimal performance would imply testing all the possible hyperparameter combinations, which is not realistic nor practical. The random-combination testing approach appears to be more practical.

²³<https://wandb.ai/site/sweeps>.

Hi-Hats and Infilling Kicks And Snares) deal with infilling drum kit’s instrument parts. As the experiment names indicate, the Infilling Closed Hi-Hats model predicts the closed hi-hat part while the Infilling Kicks And Snares predicts the kick and/or snare parts. In the third experiment, Infilling Random, we remove a random set of musical events from the input pattern, independently of their drum kit instrument. We do this for a small percentage of the events present in the original loop (Infilling Random Low) and also for a large percentage (Infilling Random High).

In the next sections we will discuss how we generated the dataset for each task.

3.5.1 Infilling Closed Hi-Hats

The training dataset for this experiment was generated by picking the items in the GMD train split with a closed hi-hat part and processing them as described in Section 3.2.4. This experiment was conceived as a proof of concept that the MSO is an adequate input data representation for the Transformer architecture to solve the infilling task. For this reason, we only predict one instrument (the closed hi-hat) and use one soundfont for synthesizing the input audio loops. The underlying reason behind choosing the closed hi-hat for the proof of concept lies in that it is an instrument largely present in the loops (26.5% of the hits in the GMD) but, roughly speaking, does not carry the weight of marking the beat and backbeat as the kick and snare commonly do.

In order to quantitatively evaluate the suitability of the MSO as input data representation, we compare the results of this experiment with an equivalent experiment in which the inputs are the HVOs of the input patterns.

Since some of the items in the GMD train split did not have a closed hi-hat part, the resulting training dataset, consisting of 15036 items, is smaller than the original GMD train split (16195 items).

3.5.2 Infilling Kicks And Snares

In this experiment, the infilling task consists in predicting the kick and/or the snare part of the input audio loop. Instead of feeding loops to the model that simultaneously lack the kick and snare parts, we train the model with a dataset that contains items with multiple incomplete versions of the same GMD performance: (A) without kick, (B) without snare, and (C) without kick and snare. Thus, we expect the model to robustly learn the roles of the kick and the snare in the pattern, which could be a harder task if both instruments are removed simultaneously. However, this strategy also results in the training dataset containing multiple incomplete variations of the same performance²⁴. The kicks and the snares often mark, respectively, the beat and the backbeat in the pattern. For this reason, it appears to be a harder task than predicting only the closed hi-hats in loops that already have the kicks and snares ‘skeleton’.

The audio loops are synthesized using 25 different soundfonts²⁵ that include acoustic as well as digital drum kits. We incorporate different types of soundfonts in order to emulate the variability of real drum kits, as it is typically done in ADT [55].

For each item in the original GMD train split, we generate a total of 6 items by combining the removal of kicks and snares with different soundfonts for audio synthesis. We select a subset of 3 soundfonts from the 25 available, and combine each soundfont with the three²⁶ possibilities for removing instruments: (A) kick, (B) snare, and (C) kick and snare, which results in 9 possible combinations (3 instrument combinations \times 3 soundfonts). From these 9 combinations we sample the 6 final instrument and soundfont combination. We could have directly randomly combined 6 soundfonts

²⁴The implications of this will be discussed in detail in Section 5.3

²⁵The soundfonts are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

²⁶This is for the general case in which the loop pattern has both kicks and snares parts. If it lacks one of the instruments (i.e., kicks or snares), we only remove the other one (i.e., snares or kicks), and if it lacks both, we discard the item. In short, we do not try to infill an instrument part that was not originally present in the original performance, since the ground truth would be an empty pattern.

with 6 incomplete pattern variations, but the intuition behind limiting the soundfont variability is to try to prioritize the learning of the patterns over the drum kit sound variability. In total, we generate a 63329 items training dataset, 4.2 times larger than the Infilling Closed Hi-Hats dataset.

3.5.3 Infilling Random

Instead of learning how to predict drum kit instrument parts, in the Infilling Random experiment, the model learns to predict hits in the pattern without an instrument constrain, i.e., the model can predict hits for all instruments in the drum kit. We generate the training dataset by removing a random percentage of hits (with their associated velocities and offsets) of each GMD performance.

Generally speaking, each genre in the dataset has a characteristic pattern for playing a particular instrument. If we average the score part of that instrument in that particular genre, we will obtain the average characteristic pattern. Following this idea, the velocity heatmap in Figure 3.6 shows the probability distribution resulting from averaging the pattern from a particular instrument across performances belonging to a particular genre. In such heatmaps, which we will discuss in the next chapters of this thesis, the x-axis corresponds to the timestep and the y-axis corresponds to the velocity value. Clusters in the heatmap indicate the velocity and timestep at which hits commonly appear, i.e., the characteristic average patterns. Intuitively, in the previous infilling experiments, in which full instrument parts are infilled, we assume that what the model is learning is something similar to such probability distributions for the instrument to infill. However, if we remove random events pertaining to different instruments in the kit, it could be interpreted that the model needs to learn these patterns for all instruments, which is arguably a more complex task than the former cases.

In order to remove a random number of events from the score, we give each hit in

Figure 3.6: Velocity heatmap example for a particular genre. Each vertical line corresponds to a timestep, and a higher value in the vertical axes indicates a higher velocity value. Clusters not centered in the vertical lines indicate an offset with respect to the closest timestep, and white areas indicate that there is not hits present in that range in the genre examples.

the score a value sampled from an homogeneous distribution. If the given value is above a threshold, the hit is kept, and otherwise, removed. In order to add further variability to the percentage of removed hits, the threshold is sampled from a range of possible values. This is done 4 times for each item in the GMD train split. Each of these 4 items is synthesized with a soundfont randomly chosen across the 25 available soundfonts. The resulting training dataset size is 64167, 4.3 times larger than the Infilling Closed Hi-Hats task.

With the purpose of evaluating the impact of the percentage of removed hits on the model performance, we endure two trainings:

- Infilling Random Low (IRL): In which between 10% and 30% of the hits in the original GMD score are removed.
- Infilling Random High (IRH): In which between 40% and 70% of the hits in the original GMD score are removed.

In the extreme cases in which the 70% of the events are removed, very little information remains in the score and thus, in the input audio loop. Moreover, since the removed events are randomly chosen, the remaining part (the input to the model) is most likely not very musically meaningful. In a practical use case in the context of a compositional setting, the input pattern given to the system by the composer would probably provide a more musically meaningful context. However, by training

on a large amount of data we expect the model to understand the internal coherence of the drum loops and be able to respond robustly to musically meaningful inputs.

Chapter 4

Hyperparameter tuning

The main challenge of a machine learning model is being able to generalize, i.e., perform well on new, previously unseen inputs. This is what differentiates machine learning from an optimization problem, in which we only try to fit a function to a known dataset. In machine learning, the generalization error is estimated by computing the error between the expected output and the prediction output on an unseen dataset during training [4].

The performance of a machine learning model can be estimated by addressing its ability to (1) minimize the training error (avoid underfitting) (2) minimize the gap between the training and the test error (avoid overfitting). Whether a model will overfit or underfit after a number of epochs depends on the model's capacity. The model's capacity is "its ability to fit a wide variety of functions" [4]. A model with low capacity will probably underfit (not fit the training set) and a model with high capacity might overfit (fit the training set so well that it can only predict accurately with inputs from the training dataset, in other words, not generalize well). As Goodfellow et al. [4] state: "while simpler functions are more likely to generalize (to have a small gap between training and test error), we must still choose a sufficiently complex hypothesis to achieve low training error".

In order to find an adequate capacity for our models, we perform a hyperparameter tuning phase in which we determine the best set of hyperparameters by training several instances of the same model using randomly selected hyperparameters among a predetermined set of values. We evaluate the adequacy of each hyperparameter selection by studying the model’s performance on both the train and test dataset, with the aim of finding a hyperparameter combination that both (1) minimizes the training error and (2) generalizes well.

As discussed in Section 3.4.3, we conduct a hyperparameter tuning study using the sweep tool in W&B [60], that trains different instances of the same model with a random selection of hyperparameters for 100 epochs. We call each instance a sweep. The ranges across which the values of the parameters are randomly sampled are shown in Table 4.1¹. The optimizer was fixed to the stochastic gradient descent (sgd) after a number of informal sweeps with both sgd and the Adam optimizer that resulted in a persistent sgd better performance.

Domain	Hyperparameter	Values
Transformer Architecture	Model embedding dimension	Cat {16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512}
	Number of encoder blocks	\mathcal{U} {6, 12}
	Number of multi-head attention heads	Cat {1, 2, 4, 8, 16}
	Feedforward layer dimension	Cat {16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512}
	Dropout value	\mathcal{U} [0.1, 0.3]
Training	Learning rate	\mathcal{U} [0, 0.1]
	Batch size	Cat {16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512}
	Hit loss penalty (w)	\mathcal{U} [0, 1]
	Optimizer (fixed)	Stochastic gradient descent (sgd)

Table 4.1: Hyperparameter ranges for tuning sweeps.

Using the experiment tracking tools described in Section 3.4.2, at the end of the 100

¹Mathematical notation: $\mathcal{U}\{a, b\}$ corresponds to a discrete uniform distribution in range $\{a, \dots, b\}$, where a and b are both integers. $\mathcal{U}[a, b]$ denotes a continuous uniform distribution in range (a, b) . Cat $\{a, b, \dots, c\}$ denotes a categorical distribution in the set of values $\{a, b, \dots, c\}$.

epochs, we calculate evaluation metrics and generate velocity heatmaps that allow a visual inspection of the distribution of hits, velocities and offsets of the predictions and the ground truths. We generate as well audios and pianorolls for a subset of the test split.

During the evaluation of the final trained models (discussed in Chapter 5), we realized that comparing the model performance after 100 epochs might have not been the ideal strategy, since in some of the experiments, the model overfits before epoch 100. Overfitting can result in a decrease in test hit accuracy and hence, in disqualifying a hyperparameter combination that could have obtained better metrics but in a previous epoch, prior to overfitting. This could have been avoided by implementing a regularization strategy (discussed in Section 5.1.1). Due to the limited amount of time and resources, the hyperparameter selection was not repeated. However, since we based our choices not only on the test set accuracy metrics but also on the informal evaluation of the generated audios and velocity heatmaps, we are confident that the choices taken were adequate.

4.1 Infilling Closed Hi-Hats

For this experiment we trained 17 instances (sweeps) of the Infilling Closed Hi-Hat model for 100 epochs, each with a different hyperparameter setup. Figure 4.1 shows the hyperparameters used for each sweep and their resulting test set hit accuracy. Each line represents a sweep, and the color scale indicates the final test hit accuracy (the lighter, the better hit accuracy). We compare the runs against the final test hit accuracy (accuracy of predicting the hits averaged across voices) since the losses are weighted differently for each experiment (w , the weighting coefficient, is a hyperparameter), and hence, are not comparable.

In Figure 4.1, it can be seen that a hit loss penalty (w) between 0.3 and 0.8 appears to give the best results. In contrast, the other parameters do not appear to show a direct

influence on the test hit accuracy (the colors appear in no particular order in the corresponding hyperparameter’s column). The impact of the hit loss penalty value in the test hit accuracy is confirmed by the hyperparameter importance study² done in W&B, in which this parameter shows the higher value. However, the statistical relevance of such studies is not clearly established due to the limited amount of conducted sweeps.

Figure 4.1: Infilling Closed Hi-Hats sweep comparison. The last column indicates the test hit accuracy. Each line refers to a sweep run and displays its hyperparameter configuration. The color represents the test hit accuracy value (lighter colors indicate higher values).

The metrics, audios, pianorolls, and heatmaps for all sweeps and both train and test sets are available in W&B³.

We will now compare the two sweeps with better test set hit accuracy: *pious-sweep-15*⁴ and *zesty-sweep-13*⁵. Table 4.2 shows the hyperparameter combination of each model. *zesty-sweep-13* has a smaller batch size, model embedding dimension and

²The importance metric is calculated by training a random forest in which the hyperparameters are the inputs and the metric is the target. A correlation study is also conducted, in which the linear correlation between the hyperparameter and the chosen metric is determined. However, as it has been already discussed, since the hit loss penalty value directly influences the loss, we expect this parameter to obtain a high correlation value, while we might be more interested in second order interactions, which can be determined by the importance metric. <https://docs.wandb.ai/ref/app/features/panels/parameter-importance>.

³https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingClosedHH/reports/Infilling-Closed-Hi-Hats-Hyperparameter-tuning--Vmlldzo50DA30TI.

⁴https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingClosedHH/runs/6ew97r1m.

⁵https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingClosedHH/runs/req6fjig.

number of encoder blocks, but a larger (double) number of attention heads and feedforward dimension. Both models have similar hit loss penalty values and relatively similar dropout values. In *pious-sweep-15*, the feedforward layer reduces the model embedding dimension, as opposed to in *zesty-sweep-13*, where the feedforward layer expands the model embedding dimension.

Hyperparameter	<i>pious-sweep-15</i>	<i>zesty-sweep-13</i>
Batch size	64	16
Model embedding dimension	256	32
Feedforward dimension	128	512
Dropout	0.16	0.24
Learning rate	0.07	0.07
Hit loss penalty (w)	0.40	0.38
Number of attention heads	8	16
Number of encoder blocks	8	6

Table 4.2: Hyperparameters for the two Infilling Closed Hi-Hats sweeps with best test hit accuracy values at epoch 100.

A visual exploration of the pianorolls indicates that, in those two sweeps, the predicted patterns are not empty. Other runs with high w sometimes predict empty patterns, since, in a score, there is generally more positions where there is not a hit occurring, so predicting the pattern full of 0 without giving more weight to the misclassification of a hit can result in a model learning to predict empty patterns while getting good metrics. As aforementioned, we evaluate every sweep in a subset of the test set, unseen during training. The subset contains 1916 2-bar items from 70 performances. In Table 4.3, we display the test set closed hi-hat hit accuracy, and their corresponding mean square error (MSE) for the velocity and the offsets. Equivalent metrics are calculated in the training set and are available in W&B.

pious-sweep-15 obtains better results in hit accuracy and velocity MSE while *zesty-sweep-13* gets a slightly lower offset MSE. However, these metrics do not give information about relevant aspects such as the variability of the patterns predicted according to the genre, which can be observed in velocity heatmaps. The velocity

Metric	pious-sweep-15	zesty-sweep-13
Closed Hi-Hat Hit Accuracy	0.747	0.726
Closed Hi-Hat Velocity MSE	0.074	0.075
Closed Hi-Hat Offset MSE	0.014	0.013

Table 4.3: Performance metrics for the two Infilling Closed Hi-Hats sweeps with highest test hit accuracy values at epoch 100.

heatmaps (Figures 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4) display the distributions of hits and their velocities and offsets in the score. The left column refers to the number of items in the test set used to generate the heatmaps, in terms of 2-bar loops (`n_loops`) and in terms of total performances (`unique_refs`)⁶.

Figure 4.2 shows the ground truth velocity heatmaps. It can be appreciated that patterns are very distinct across genres, and that the genres with more items in the subset coming from various performances (i.e., soul, rock and funk) show more green areas, which suggests the variability in the patterns across performances in the test set belonging to the same genre. Due to this data imbalance, it is hard to extract solid conclusions only by visual exploration of the heatmaps, but in both sweeps (Figures 4.3 and 4.4), we can observe that both prediction patterns show limited velocity and offset ranges: the velocity range is shorter than in the ground truth (there much more white areas in the prediction) and the hits are closer to the vertical lines than they are in the ground truth. Finally, while *pious-sweep-15* obtained slightly better metrics than *zesty-sweep-13*, *pious-sweep-15* shows very similar patterns across genres, while the predicted patterns by *zesty-sweep-13* show higher variability across genres, which makes it more resembling to the ground truth. For this reason, even though, as aforementioned, *pious-sweep-15* obtained slightly better metrics, we choose the *zesty-sweep-13* hyperparameter set for the Closed Hi-hat experiment.

⁶It should be noted that the imbalances between those numbers indicate the imbalances in the test set and not in the training set. A comparison between data imbalances in each dataset split is shown in Table 3.1.

Figure 4.2: Closed Hi-Hats Velocity Heatmaps. Test Set, Ground Truth.

Figure 4.3: Closed Hi-Hats Velocity Heatmaps. Test Set, *pious-sweep-15* Predictions.

Figure 4.4: Closed Hi-Hats Velocity Heatmaps. Test Set, *zesty-sweep-13* Predictions.

4.2 Infilling Kicks And Snares

For this experiment we ran 19 sweeps. Metrics, audios, pianorolls and heatmaps are available in W&B⁷. The hyperparameter combinations used in the 10 sweeps with highest test hit accuracies are shown in Figure 4.5. It appears that models with a model embedding dimension of 256 and a learning rate between 0.07 and 0.09 obtain the best values. The parameter importance study (available in W&B) shows that the two parameters more important for obtaining a high test hit accuracy are the number of attention heads and the hit loss penalty.

Figure 4.5: Infilling Kicks And Snares sweep comparison of the 10 sweeps with highest test hit accuracy metrics.

The test subset is larger (8157 items) than in the previous experiment due to the dataset processing techniques described in Section 3.5.2. The imbalance between genres is conserved after the augmentation.

The sweep with the highest test hit accuracy metric is *efficient-sweep-9*⁸, that also achieves the lowest velocity MSE for both kick and snare. The second best sweep, *fancy-sweep-2*⁹, in test hit accuracy does not perform best in any metric. In Ta-

⁷https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingKicksAndSnares/reports/Infilling-Kicks-And-Snares-Hyperparameter-tuning--Vmlldzo50DA3Njg.

⁸https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingKicksAndSnares/runs/p04uwx0x.

⁹https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingKicksAndSnares/runs/gjzbt4uz.

ble 4.4, we show the hyperparameters for those two sweeps. Both models have the same batch size, model embedding dimension and number of attention heads. It is particularly interesting that the number of heads is very small (2) in comparison with the values giving the best metrics in the Infilling Closed Hi-Hats experiment (16 heads). *fancy-sweep-2* has a larger feedforward dimension and number of encoder blocks and a smaller dropout and hit loss penalty. The hit loss penalty value in *fancy-sweep-2* is closer to the value of chosen for the Infilling Closed Hi-Hats experiment (0.38).

Hyperparameter	efficient-sweep-9	fancy-sweep-2
Batch size	32	32
Model embedding dimension	256	256
Feedforward dimension	512	2048
Dropout	0.30	0.16
Learning rate	0.09	0.07
Hit loss penalty (w)	0.73	0.46
Number of attention heads	2	2
Number of encoder blocks	6	8

Table 4.4: Hyperparameters for the two Infilling Kicks And Snares sweeps with highest test hit accuracy values at epoch 100.

In all metrics (Table 4.5), *efficient-sweep-9* performs better. In comparison with the other 18 sweeps, this run also had the best overall metrics except in offsets. We now compare the velocity heatmaps from both sweeps, with the aim of informally establishing differences in the distributions learned by each sweep. This model generates both kicks and snares, but for the sake of brevity we will only compare the snares heatmaps. The kicks heatmaps can be found online and are more similar across the sweeps than that of the snares.

The ground truth velocity heatmaps for the snare in the ground truth are shown in Figure 4.6. Figure 4.7 and Figure 4.8 show the heatmaps for the predicted snares in *efficient-sweep-9* and *fancy-sweep-2* respectively. In contrast to the Infilling Closed Hi-Hats sweeps, both models show an adequate velocity range. Since white areas in

Metric	efficient-sweep-9	fancy-sweep-2
Kick Hit Accuracy	0.859	0.842
Snare Hit Accuracy	0.831	0.820
Kick Offset MSE	0.006	0.006
Snare Offset MSE	0.010	0.011
Kick Velocity MSE	0.028	0.029
Snare Velocity MSE	0.048	0.053

Table 4.5: Performance metrics for the two Infilling Kicks And Snares sweeps with highest test hit accuracy values at epoch 100.

the heatmap indicate that there are no hits predicted in that range, the apparently more accurate velocity range might be due the higher test set size and not to a better ability of the model in its prediction. Similarly to the Infilling Closed Hi-Hats sweeps, both *efficient-sweep-9* and *fancy-sweep-2* display very small offsets (the clusters are closer to the vertical lines¹⁰). Furthermore, *efficient-sweep-9* shows less dense heatmaps (less green) than *fancy-sweep-2*, and on this basis, more similar to the ground truth. The predicted patterns in genres such as punk, afrobeat, rock or reggae differ significantly from the patterns in the ground truth. Since the rock genre has a the largest number of training examples (32.5% of the train dataset), a bad heatmap prediction might indicate that the model is underfitting, but the latin genre (17% of the training examples) appears to be well learned. This might be an indicator of the variability of patterns in a genre inside the dataset more than the ability of the model to learn the genres patterns.

We choose the *efficient-sweep-9* hyperparameter configuration due to their better performance in the evaluated metrics in comparison to the *fancy-sweep-2*. Moreover, the predicted heatmaps appear to be more similar in terms of density (green areas) to the ground truth heatmaps.

¹⁰This can be easily established when plotting the hits as dots on the heatmap, but this hinders visualizing the distributions. This can be done interactively W&B.

Figure 4.6: Infilling Kicks And Snares Velocity Heatmaps. Test Set, Snare Ground Truth.

Figure 4.7: Infilling Kicks And Snares Velocity Heatmaps. Test Set, Snare *efficient-sweep-9* Predictions.

Figure 4.8: Infilling Kicks And Snares Velocity Heatmaps. Test Set, Snare *fancy-sweep-2* Predictions.

4.3 Infilling Random

The hyperparameter tuning for the Infilling Random experiment was conducted on different instances of the model with the Infilling Random High (IRH) dataset (i.e., lacking between 40% and 70% of the original hits in the performance). Here, we only performed 6 sweeps due to time and computational resources constraints. Figure 4.9 shows the different parameter configuration for each sweep and the final test hit accuracy. The parameters of each run are specified in Table 4.6. Due to the reduced number of sweeps, it is complicated to establish which range of parameters are more adequate. As with the previous experiments, metrics, audios, pianorolls and heatmaps are available in W&B¹¹.

Figure 4.9: Infilling Random sweep comparison.

As occurred with the Infilling Kicks And Snares sweeps, the test subset is larger (8191 items) than in the Infilling Closed Hi-Hat sweeps due to the dataset processing techniques described in Section 3.5.3. Again, the imbalance between genres is conserved after the augmentation.

*magic-sweep-4*¹² shows not only the best test hit average accuracy but also the lowest offset MSE and velocity MSE. The second and third sweeps with best test hit

¹¹https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/reports/Infilling-Random-Hyperparameter-tuning--Vmlldzo50DA4MTI.

¹²https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/runs/r431luo6t.

Hyper-parameter	magic-sweep-4	fallen-sweep-3	crimson-sweep-2	faithful-sweep-6	still-sweep-1	major-sweep-5
Batch size	32	512	256	64	64	64
Model embedding dim.	32	128	512	16	16	32
Feedforward dim.	16	64	64	128	16	16
Dropout	0.18	0.17	0.11	0.12	0.18	0.19
Learning rate	0.094	0.098	0.065	0.011	0.094	0.039
Hit loss penalty (w)	0.47	0.90	0.35	0.15	0.13	0.04
Number of attention heads	4	4	16	8	8	8
Number of encoder blocks	6	12	12	9	9	6
Test hit accuracy	0.935	0.933	0.933	0.842	0.797	0.626
Test offset MSE	0.0028	0.0029	0.0029	0.0030	0.0033	0.0039
Test velocity MSE	0.0193	0.0248	0.0248	0.0294	0.0324	0.0645

Table 4.6: Hyperparameters and performance metrics at epoch 100 for the Infilling Random sweeps.

average accuracy metrics (*fallen-sweep-3*¹³ and *crimson-sweep-2*¹⁴) returned empty heatmaps, which indicates that the model predicted empty hits. Both models have relatively large batch sizes and number of encoder blocks but very different learning rates, hit loss penalty and number of attention layers. The large difference in the hit loss penalty is of interest since, even with this large variation, none of those sweeps predicted any hit. In contrast, *magic-sweep-4*, a much smaller model (with a smaller model embedding and feedforward dimensions), appears to be learning better since it does predict hits. In the generated heatmaps, the models *faithful-sweep-6*¹⁵, *still-sweep-1*¹⁶ and *major-sweep-5*¹⁷ show distributions very similar across genres and with not much variability. Figure 4.10 shows the ground truth heatmaps for the kicks and Figure 4.11 shows the corresponding prediction heatmaps from *magic-*

¹³https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/runs/1grc8hg1.

¹⁴https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/runs/qldedj26.

¹⁵https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/runs/jol6qajv.

¹⁶https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/runs/ziyeudvj.

¹⁷https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/runs/q4eykjwh.

sweep-4. Although *magic-sweep-4* scores best metrics, it still does not show a very high variability in the heatmaps. Since the model is also very small, we suspect that the model might not have enough capacity to learn the task, which we suspect, as discussed in Section 3.5.3, the most complex among the presented. For this reason, we select the parameters from the winning sweep in the Infilling Kicks And Snares experiment, the *efficient-sweep-9*, and expect that the good results in the Infilling Kicks And Snares can extend to the Infilling Random task.

Figure 4.10: Infilling Random Velocity Heatmaps. Test Set, Kick Ground Truth.

Figure 4.11: Infilling Random Velocity Heatmaps. Test Set, Kick *magic-sweep-4* Predictions.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

In the previous chapter, we determined the hyperparameter combination for each infilling experiment. In the following sections, we evaluate the performance of the corresponding trained models.

Music generation systems are frequently evaluated in subjective listening experiments. A standard procedure consists in conducting a musical Turing test in which subjects are asked to determine if the generated piece was composed by a human or a machine. Still, many of these studies confound the two questions of whether the piece could have been composed by a human and whether it is aesthetically pleasant [18]. Moreover, statistically relevant experiments require a significant amount of resources for recruiting a significant and relevant sample size (e.g., with different musical backgrounds, often not reported in such studies [18]). Furthermore, often each study is tailored to a particular system, which makes the reported results not comparable across different generative systems.

A musical Turing test of an infilling system presents the additional difficulty that the system does not compose full pieces but instrument parts or patterns that are intended to be played or heard along with the system input. However, if the gen-

erated parts were to be listened along with the input parts, the evaluation would be most likely biased by the presence of non-generated content (the input). Perhaps a more appropriate subjective evaluation of an infilling system would be in the context of its usage as a co-creation tool. Briot et al. [5] suggest the satisfaction of the composer as a subjective evaluation criteria: “notably, if the assistance of the computer allowed him to compose and create music that he may consider not having been possible otherwise”. Yet such evaluation requires a user interface and preferably some control parameters¹, that is, a usable system, which falls out of the scope of this thesis.

Due to the aforementioned limitations of a subjective evaluation of our model, we opt for an objective evaluation methodology that reports comparable metrics across systems and accounts for reproducibility. We do not attempt to evaluate the creativity of the system or its performance in a co-creation context, as the system should first be able to comply with the technical and formal expectations [18].

5.1 Evaluation method

As discussed in Chapter 4, the main challenge of a machine learning system is to generalize, i.e., to learn patterns in the training data that are not specific to it and generalize to unseen inputs. In the hyperparameter tuning section, we selected the best hyperparameters by comparing the model’s performance in the test set. Hence, the examples in the test set are used to improve the model performance and consequently, in order to avoid bias, the model needs to be evaluated in a different set. For this reason, we evaluate our models in a dataset split unseen during training and in the hyperparameter tuning phase, the validation set². It should be noted that

¹This will be discussed as further work in Chapter 6.

²In the literature, the hyperparameter tuning is generally done on the validation set and the evaluation is conducted on the test set. However, in the GMD dataset both test and validation split have a balanced across genres and similar number of examples, so it is indifferent to use the test set for the hyperparameter tuning phase and the validation set for the evaluation, as we did in this work.

the train, test and validation splits proceed from the same dataset, and hence, the notion of ‘generalization’ should be taken carefully. The robustness of the model to unseen inputs from other datasets should be further evaluated.

During training, we periodically log the evaluation metrics to W&B³, which allow diagnosing the models during training. Additionally, audios, pianorolls and heatmaps are periodically logged, so that the model predictions can be compared against the ground truth at different training stages.

5.1.1 Early stopping as a regularization strategy

While optimization strategies focus on reducing the training error, regularization strategies concentrate on reducing the generalization error, frequently at expense of the training error [4]. For our experiments, we use a simple regularizer: early stopping. This strategy can be understood as treating the number of training epochs also as a hyperparameter, and choosing the value that gets a minimum generalization error. In practice, this means that we set a large number of epochs in our training algorithm and save the model periodically. During training, we observe the learning curves in order to select the epoch that has the minimum validation error, and as our final trained model we return the model at this “early stopped” epoch. Early stopping is not only in analogy but also formally a regularizer [4] since it limits the effective capacity of the model.

5.1.2 Evaluation metrics

Once the best set of learned parameters for the model has been determined in early stopping, we evaluate the model performance on the validation set. We distinguish between (1) probabilistic measures without music domain knowledge and (2) probabilistic metrics based on musical domain knowledge [18]. These metrics asses

³For this purpose, we use the GrooveEvaluator library (<https://github.com/behzadhaki/GrooveEvaluator>), coded by Behzad Haki and adapted by the author to the Infilling Task.

technical properties of the generated music and help identify the characteristics of the generated music. It is important to report diverse metrics since in general, performing well in one metric does not imply that the system will perform well under different criteria [62].

Additionally, we compare the generated heatmaps for each task against the ground truth heatmaps. Due to time constraints, no objective quantitative evaluation has been conducted for comparing the distributions, but nevertheless the heatmaps are still informative in terms of velocity range, offsets range and variability across genre.

We do not compare the evaluation metrics to any other reported metrics by other authors since the only comparable model in the literature is the one by Gillick et al. [11], which conducts a listening test for evaluation but does not report any quantitative metrics for the infilling task.

Probabilistic metrics without music domain knowledge

- **Hit accuracy:** Proportion of correctly predicted hits among the total number of predicted hits.
- **Hit perplexity:** The perplexity is calculated as an exponentiation of the binary hit cross-entropy and it is an indicator of the generalization performance of a prediction model. The intuition behind it can be illustrated by comparing a 6-faced die and a human. Given the first two numbers (1,2) of the series of counting from 1 to 6, a human will most likely do the right prediction (3) as the next item in the sequence, whereas a die will only predict the right number $1/6$ of the times. As a result, the human's perplexity is lower than a die's perplexity. In language models, perplexity is used to evaluate how well the model understands how a language works, e.g., if the model is assigning higher probability to sentences grammatically and syntactically correct. Measuring the perplexity in the validation dataset is a common way of measuring the

generalization performance.

- **Offset and velocity MSE:** Mean square error (defined in Section 3.4.1).

Probabilistic metrics based on musical domain knowledge

The following metrics address rhythm features as well as similarity features and are collected in Bruford et al [63]. Here, we report the descriptive statistics of these metrics (mean, median, standard deviation and range) for comparison across models.

- **Number of instruments (NoI):** Number of instruments in the drum kit with active hits. This measure is trivial for the instrument infilling task (it is known in advance), but might be informative for the Infilling Random task. Ranges from 1 to 9.
- **Average voice density:** Average of number of instruments divided by total number of instruments in the drum kit (9) over all timesteps. Similarly to the NoI, trivial for instrument infilling tasks but perhaps informative for the Infilling Random task. Ranges from 0 to 1.
- **Total step density:** Ratio of total timesteps in which there is at least one hit. Ranges from 0 to 1.
- **Velocity Similarity Score:** Measures the symmetry of the pattern at bar-level. We compare the velocities of the hits occurring at the same bar-level positions in the first and the second bar. Ranges from 0 to 1.
- **Weak to Strong Ratio:** Ratio of number of hits occurring at weak beats (downbeats) to number of hits occurring at strong beats [64]. If larger than 1, weak beats are predominant, if lower than 1, strong beats are predominant.

- **Autocorrelation curve descriptive statistics:** The velocity autocorrelation curve is calculated per voice and then added up per step. The descriptive statistics of the autocorrelation curve are informative about various aspects of the periodicity of pattern [65]:
 - **Skewness:** The skewness of a probability distribution measures its asymmetry with respect to the mean value. A skewed distribution indicates strong periodicities at a certain level, e.g., at the bar level but not at the beat level [65].
 - **Centroid:** The geometric center of the distribution indicates, similarly to skewness, important levels of periodicity [65].
 - **Maximum:** The maximum value is a measure of how strong the periodicity in the velocity is [65].

5.2 Infilling Closed Hi-Hats

In this experiment we train the Transformer Groove Infilling model to predict the closed hi-hat part of an input loop that did not previously have it. As means of evaluating the performance of the MSO as input audio representation, we train an equivalent model that uses the HVO as input data representation instead. The metrics collected during training as well as the generated pianorolls and audios are available in W&B⁴.

⁴MSO model: https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingClosedHH/reports/Infilling-Closed-Hi-Hats-MSO-Training--Vm1ldzo5Nzg5NTk. HVO model: https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingClosedHH/reports/Infilling-Closed-Hi-Hats-HVO-Training--Vm1ldzo5Nzg5MzI.

5.2.1 Learning curves

MSO model early stopping

Figure 5.1 displays the variation of the training and validation loss over the epochs for the model with MSO as input data representation. The curves are smoothed with a rolling average⁵. Initially, both losses descend jointly up to epoch 90, where the validation loss stagnates whereas the training loss continues descending. Circa epoch 120, the validation loss starts to increase, which indicates that the model is learning patterns specific to the training dataset that do not generalize to the validation dataset, i.e., the model overfits. Since the validation loss shows its minimum value at epoch 110 we select this epoch as the optimal epoch for early stopping.

Figure 5.1: MSO Infilling Closed Hi-Hats. Validation (orange) and training (blue) loss.

HVO model early stopping

The learning curves for the HVO model are shown in Figure 5.2. Similar to the MSO model, both curves initially descend jointly up to a point in which the validation loss stagnates whereas the training loss maintains a descending tendency. The minimum

⁵The rolling average or simple moving average (SMA) replaces each data point by an average over a window centered in that point.

validation loss occurs at epoch 70 and hence, we select this epoch as the optimal point for early stopping.

Figure 5.2: HVO Infilling Closed Hi-Hats. Validation (orange) and training (blue) loss.

5.2.2 Evaluation metrics

Probabilistic metrics without music domain knowledge

Table 5.1 displays the accuracy, MSE and perplexity metrics of both the MSO and HVO versions of the Transformer Groove Infilling. The reported values correspond to the smoothed curves, that is, to the running average at the corresponding early stopped epoch. The accuracy metrics are moderately good in the case of the HVO model, with 79.7% of the hits predicted correctly and slightly lower in the MSO model, with a 75.4% instead. The decrease in the accuracy (-4.3%) for the MSO model with respect to the HVO model is considerably low taking into account that the MSO representation is obtained directly from the audio data and does not require a transcription or tokenization, as discussed in Section 3.2.2. This difference is also low in the case of the velocity and offset MSE. Finally, the lower perplexity value in the HVO model suggests that the model generalizes better.

	MSO model	HVO model
Closed Hi-Hats Hit Accuracy	0.754	0.797
Closed Hi-Hats Velocity MSE	0.074	0.062
Closed Hi-Hats Offset MSE	0.014	0.014
Hit perplexity	1.358	1.316

Table 5.1: Probabilistic metrics without music domain knowledge. Evaluated on the validation set.

Probabilistic metrics with music domain knowledge

In Table 5.2 and Table 5.3 we compare the musically informed probabilistic metrics for the MSO and HVO version of the Transformer Groove Infilling. Both the total step density and the velocity similarity score statistics are similar between the MSO and the HVO model. The large mean values of the total step density show that both models tend to predict more hits than the present in the ground truth. This might be motivated by the hit loss penalty factor (w) that provides a higher reward to the good prediction of a hit than the absence of a hit. Both MSO and HVO model exhibit a high mean velocity similarity score, that indicates that the variations between the second bars compared to the first ones are less than those of the ground truth. Finally, the ground truth has in average 2.6 hits at weak beat for each hit in strong beat, while in the HVO model there are almost as much weak as strong hits, whereas in the MSO model this ratio is moderately higher. The low standard deviation in both MSO and HVO models indicate that the prediction model is less variable in this ratio.

Table 5.3 shows the descriptive statistics of the autocorrelation curve. The ground truth centroid mean value is 8, which indicates that the periodicity at half-bar level is relevant. The mean centroid value is moderately larger in the prediction models. Overall, both MSO and HVO models show similar statistics and the ground truth metrics have a higher standard deviation, which might indicate that the prediction models have less variability in their periodicity levels.

		mean	std	min	max	median
Total Step Density	GT	0.37	0.22	0.03	1.00	0.28
	P MSO	0.47	0.27	0.12	1.00	0.38
	P HVO	0.48	0.28	0.00	1.00	0.41
Velocity Similarity Score	GT	0.77	0.32	0.00	1.00	0.91
	P MSO	0.95	0.03	0.00	1.00	0.96
	P HVO	0.94	0.10	0.00	1.00	0.96
Weak-to-Strong Ratio	GT	2.59	7.27	0.00	112.24	0.70
	P MSO	1.67	2.55	0.00	15.65	0.93
	P HVO	1.10	1.43	0.00	17.54	0.88

Table 5.2: Probabilistic metrics with music domain knowledge. GT: Ground Truth, P: Predictions.

		mean	std	min	max	median
Skewness	GT	2.12	1.01	0.09	5.39	1.97
	P MSO	1.35	0.85	0.00	3.40	1.36
	P HVO	1.36	0.92	0.00	5.39	1.23
Centroid	GT	8.15	2.25	0.00	11.31	8.85
	P MSO	9.13	0.72	5.38	10.7	9.32
	P HVO	9.17	0.98	0.00	16.00	9.36
Max	GT	3.88	3.06	0.02	18.27	3.23
	P MSO	3.15	2.09	0.45	11.17	2.46
	P HVO	3.40	2.02	0.00	10.15	2.89

Table 5.3: Descriptive statistics of the Autocorrelation curve. GT: Ground Truth, P: Predictions.

5.2.3 Velocity heatmaps

Finally, we present the velocity heatmaps from the ground truth and the HVO and MSO predictions (Figures 5.3 and 5.4). The most significant difference between the predictions and the ground truth is the velocity range, which is reduced in the case of the predictions. The prediction models show variation across genres, but not as strong as the variation present in the ground truth. This might be due to the genre imbalance in the training dataset, that might cause the model learning the patterns present in the most frequent genres (such as funk) and extrapolating them to less frequent genres (such as pop). Lastly, the clusters appear centered in vertical

lines, which indicates very low offsets in comparison to the ground truth. Overall, it appears that the patterns learnt by the MSO model are less rigid (which does not imply better) since there are less clusters as opposed to the HVO version. An objective comparison is further required in order to obtain the similarity between the predicted and the ground truth heatmaps.

Figure 5.3: Infilling Closed Hi-Hats Velocity Heatmaps. Validation Set, Ground Truth.

Figure 5.4: Infilling Closed Hi-Hats Velocity Heatmaps. Validation Set, Predictions.

5.3 Infilling Kicks And Snares

In the Infilling Kicks And Snares experiment we train the Transformer Groove Infilling to predict the kicks and/or snares for an audio drum loop. The metrics collected during training, as well as pianorolls, audios and heatmaps, are available in W&B⁶.

5.3.1 Learning curves

Figure 5.5 displays the train and validation loss progress during training. The validation loss descends steadily down to epoch 60, where it stagnates and gradually increases back, whereas the training loss maintains a descending tendency. We early stop the model at epoch 60 where the validation loss reaches its minimum. In contrast to the previous experiment, the validation loss exhibits important peaks.

Another significant aspect of the learning curves is the pronounced gap existing between training and validation loss. The fact that both losses jointly decrease in the first epochs shows that the model is learning correctly, but the gap indicates that the training data is predicted considerably more successfully. This can not be justified by overfitting since the validation loss decreases before epoch 60. A more likely explanation is that the training dataset is too specific. As explained in Section 3.5.2, the training dataset for this task is generated by removing kicks and/or snares from each example in the GMD, i.e., different variations of the same item in the GMD are present in the training dataset. Those patterns might still apply to the validation dataset since its loss does not augment, however, it appears that some sort of “transformation overfitting” [66] might be occurring, equivalently to behaviors displayed in systems with strong data augmentation strategies in which the system learns the augmentation strategy and performs worse on real data. Some approaches to test and prevent this behavior are presented as future work in Chapter 6.

⁶https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingKicksAndSnares/reports/Infilling-Kicks-And-Snares-Training--Vmlldzo5Nzg50TI.

Figure 5.5: Infilling Kicks And Snares. Validation (orange) and training (blue) loss.

5.3.2 Evaluation metrics

Probabilistic metrics without music domain knowledge

In Table 5.4 we display the evaluation metrics without music domain knowledge. The mean hit accuracy is significantly higher than in the case of the MSO Infilling Closed Hi-Hats model (+8%). Even if the model is learning, as aforementioned, patterns too specific to the training dataset, the validation set is still unseen during training, so the evaluation metrics are agnostic to this matter. The improvement in the accuracy might be due to the larger size of the dataset (about 4 times larger) or due to the nature of the model’s task itself, that benefits from learning kicks and snares jointly. Another reason for this considerable increase in accuracy could be that the kicks and snare patterns are less variable across genres and therefore, easier to learn for a prediction model. It is noteworthy that the Infilling Kicks And Snares model, in turn, obtains a higher perplexity value than the Infilling Closed Hi-Hats. Since the Infilling Kicks And Snares obtains a higher accuracy measure in the validation set, the difference in the perplexity metrics could indicate the difference in the grammars of the instruments to be predicted. The Infilling Kicks

And Snares has to predict either kicks, or snares, or both, so there is a larger space of possibilities, plausible with a higher perplexity value. Finally, the model achieves better results for the kick than for the snare part in terms of accuracy, velocity MSE and offset MSE.

Kicks Hit Accuracy	0.857
Snares Hit Accuracy	0.810
Mean Hit Accuracy	0.834
Kicks Velocity MSE	0.041
Snares Velocity MSE	0.064
Mean Velocity MSE	0.053
Kicks Offset MSE	0.007
Snares Offset MSE	0.010
Mean Offset MSE	0.009
Hit perplexity	2.043

Table 5.4: Probabilistic metrics without music domain knowledge. Evaluated on the validation set.

Probabilistic metrics with music domain knowledge

The musically informed evaluation metrics are shown in Table 5.5 and Table 5.6. The model achieves very similar metrics to the ground truth in the case of the total step density and the velocity similarity score, with a slightly smaller standard deviation in the case of the velocity similarity. The mean predicted weak-to-strong ratio is significantly smaller than the ground truth and the predicted distribution has also a smaller standard deviation and range. The autocorrelation curve descriptive statistics are shown in Table 5.6. Ground truth and prediction display very similar skewness metrics and centroid metrics, and a slight variation in maximum value. It appears that the model predicts patterns with stronger periodicities in the velocity profile.

		mean	std	min	max	median
Total Step Density	GT	0.36	0.23	0.03	1.00	0.31
	P	0.38	0.26	0.00	1.00	0.28
Velocity Similarity Score	GT	0.81	0.30	0.00	1.00	0.93
	P	0.91	0.17	0.00	1.00	0.95
Weak-to-Strong Ratio	GT	2.04	4.75	0.00	75.20	1.03
	P	1.04	2.00	0.00	50.35	0.41

Table 5.5: Probabilistic metrics with music domain knowledge. GT: Ground Truth, P: Predictions.

		mean	std	min	max	median
Skewness	GT	2.62	1.00	0.06	5.39	2.77
	P	2.36	1.08	0.00	5.39	2.53
Centroid	GT	7.97	1.96	0.00	11.33	8.35
	P	8.09	1.76	0.00	16.00	8.28
Max	GT	4.86	3.66	0.03	21.79	4.01
	P	3.00	2.11	0.00	13.19	2.72

Table 5.6: Descriptive statistics of the Autocorrelation curve. GT: Ground Truth, P: Predictions.

5.3.3 Velocity heatmaps

Figures 5.6 and 5.7 show the velocity heatmaps for the kick and the snare respectively. Overall, compared to the Infilling Closed Hi-Hats experiment, it appears that the velocity ranges are better learnt, which is probably due to the larger training dataset. The offsets, as also occurred in the previous experiment, are rigid in the predictions in comparison to the ground truth. This suggests that the model is not learning the offsets properly, since while the average offset MSE is lower than the velocity MSE, the velocity range seems to be well predicted whereas the offset range does not. It is difficult to extract conclusions about variability across genre by visual comparisons on the kicks, but in the case of the snares, the model appears to predict patterns that are a mix of the latin and rock ground truth genre heatmaps. This could be explained by the fact that those two genres represent the 50% of the

training dataset, and might sustain the suspicion that the training dataset is overly specific.

Figure 5.6: Infilling Kicks And Snares, Velocity Heatmaps. Validation Set, Kick.

Figure 5.7: Infilling Kicks And Snares, Velocity Heatmaps. Validation Set, Kick.

5.4 Infilling Random

The Infilling Random experiment consists in adding hits to the input drum pattern, without imposing the hits to belong to a particular drum kit instrument. As presented in Section 3.5.3, we train two versions of the Transformer Groove Infilling model: the first version, IRL (Infilling Random Low), receives an input audio loop that lacks between the 10% and the 30% of its hits. In the second version, IRH (Infilling Random High), the audio loops lack between the 40% and the 70% of the hits originally present. The evaluation metrics, piano rolls, audios and heatmaps are available in W&B⁷.

5.4.1 Learning curves

IRL model early stopping

Figure 5.8 shows the learning curves for the Infilling Random Low experiment. In contrast to the previous experiments, here both the validation and training losses stagnate at similar values for a considerable amount of epochs. Circa epoch 120, the gap between both losses increases, but the validation loss continues gradually decreasing up to epoch 160, where it reaches its minimum and starts to steadily increase. We take 160 as the optimal epoch for early stopping.

IRH model early stopping

The learning curves for the Infilling Random High experiment can be found in Figure 5.9. Similarly to the previous experiments, after reaching the point of minimum distance between training loss and validation loss, the training loss continues to decay while the validation loss progressively augments and the model overfits. The

⁷IRL model: https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/reports/Infilling-Random-Low-IRL-Training--Vmlldzo5NzkwNTE. IRH model: https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/reports/Infilling-Random-High-IRH-Training--Vmlldzo5NzkwNDY

Figure 5.8: Infilling Random Low. Validation (orange) and training (blue) loss.

validation loss reaches its minimum at epoch 150, which we select as the early stopping epoch.

Figure 5.9: Infilling Random High. Validation (orange) and training (blue) loss.

The Infilling Random models use the same hyperparameters as the Infilling Kicks And Snare models. However, the latter was early stopped at epoch 60 whereas the Infilling Random models are stopped at epochs 150 and 160. This suggests that the Infilling Random dataset is less prone to overfit and the model can keep learning for longer.

5.4.2 Evaluation metrics

Probabilistic metrics without music domain knowledge

The averaged hit metrics across the 9 drum kit instruments can be found in Table 5.7. The hit accuracies are remarkably high, but these results should be taken carefully: in this task, the full generated score (HVO) is compared to the full score (HVO) from the ground truth. Previously, the accuracy was computed only with the the instrument(s) part(s) of interest. In contrast, here the accuracy is computed by comparing the ground truth and generated full scores. Those scores are mostly filled with zeros, since generally there are some instruments are not played or the ones that are played are only played on some timesteps (e.g. each beat). For instance, only by predicting that certain instruments are not appearing in the ground truth pattern will already give a boost to the accuracy score. Along with the difference in the task complexity, this could be a reason for which the IRL accuracy is higher: the model needs to predict less hits in an empty score. Although the accuracy difference is low (3%), the hit perplexity is considerably higher in the case of the IRH. An explanation for this could be that the IRH model receives very little information of the performance (only a few score hits are played in the input loop) and needs to understand the full ‘drum grammar’ from this. In the case of the IRL, achieving a lower perplexity appears to be easier since there is more contextual information in the input. Finally, the IRH model obtains higher MSE in the velocity and offset.

	IRL	IRH
Overall Hit Accuracy	0.977	0.947
Overall Velocity MSE	0.008	0.020
Overall Offset MSE	0.001	0.003
Hit perplexity	1.859	3.511

Table 5.7: Probabilistic metrics without music domain knowledge. Evaluated on the validation set.

Probabilistic metrics with music domain knowledge

When interpreting the musically-informed probabilistic metrics, it should be taken into account that the generated patterns are intended to be heard or played along with the input. For this reason, the output patterns are not necessarily ‘musical’ and some musically informed probabilistic metrics do not apply, such as the periodicity study in the autocorrelation curve or the velocity similarity score.

Tables 5.8 and 5.9 show the evaluation metrics of the IRL and the IRH model respectively. Both models achieve similar metrics to the ground truth except that both models fail to predict the maximum value of the weak-to-strong ratio accurately, which might indicate that the model has a limited microtiming or offset diversity. Furthermore, both models have 0 as the minimum number of instruments, which indicate that the models eventually generate empty patterns. In the case of the IRL model, the mean step density is half of the ground truth, which suggests that the IRL model predicts less hits than intended.

		mean	std	min	max	median
Number of Instruments	GT	2.91	1.11	1	7	3
	P IRL	1.93	1.03	0	6	2
Average Voice Density	GT	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.08	0.02
	P IRL	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.07	0.01
Total Step Density	GT	0.20	0.11	0.03	0.59	0.19
	P IRL	0.12	0.09	0.00	0.56	0.09
Weak-to-Strong Ratio	GT	1.81	2.96	0.00	69.17	1.02
	P IRL	1.05	2.33	0.00	33.13	0.21

Table 5.8: Infilling Random Low model. Probabilistic metrics with music domain knowledge. GT: Ground Truth, P: Predictions

5.4.3 Velocity heatmaps

Figures 5.10 and 5.11 show the ground truth and prediction heatmaps for IRL and IRH tasks respectively. We only present one the most present instrument of the

		mean	std	min	max	median
Number of Instruments	GT	3.89	1.14	1	8	4
	P IRH	3.03	0.82	0	7	3
Average Voice Density	GT	0.07	0.03	0.00	0.17	0.06
	P IRH	0.06	0.03	0.00	0.15	0.06
Total Step Density	GT	0.48	0.18	0.03	0.97	0.47
	P IRH	0.42	0.2	0.00	0.97	0.41
Weak-to-Strong Ratio	GT	1.82	2.42	0.00	96.89	1.46
	P IRH	1.43	2.41	0.00	139.35	0.95

Table 5.9: Infilling Random High model. Probabilistic metrics with music domain knowledge. GT: Ground Truth, P: Predictions

drum kit, the snare (30% of the hits in the dataset). The rest of the heatmaps are available in W&B⁸. A comparison between the ground truth patterns of the IRH (Figure 5.11) and the IRL (Figure 5.10) with the Infilling Kicks And Snares snare ground truth heatmap (Figure 5.7) reveals that the patterns are very similar and hence, the random sampling preserves the instrument pattern, as it was to be expected. Overall, the velocity ranges appear to be adequately predicted (in contrast to in the Closed Hi-Hat experiment). Contrary to the ground truth, the clusters in the prediction are densely centered around the grid lines, which indicates a very low range of offsets. In general, the obvious visual differences between ground truth and prediction indicate that even when the accuracy in the hit prediction is very high, there are still high differences in the predicted hit distributions. A quantitative evaluation of the similarity between predicted and ground truth heatmaps is yet to be conducted.

⁸IRL model: https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/reports/Infilling-Random-Low-IRL-Training--Vmlldzo5NzkwNTE. IRH model: https://wandb.ai/mmil_infilling/InfillingRandom/reports/Infilling-Random-High-IRH-Training--Vmlldzo5NzkwNDY

Figure 5.10: Infilling Random Low, Velocity Heatmaps. Validation Set, Snare.

Figure 5.11: Infilling Random High, Velocity Heatmaps. Validation Set, Snare.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and further work

6.1 Conclusions

In this thesis, we present the Transformer Groove Infilling, a deep learning model that adds instrument parts or more generally, hits, to an input audio drum loop. In addition, we introduce a novel direct audio representation as an alternative to symbolic and tokenized representations, the Multiband Synthesized Onsets (MSO). MSO allows for using audio inputs for symbolic generative models involving percussive sounds while avoiding transcription. Additionally, we release all code and configuration for further experimentation, as well as all training tracking metrics with a view to results reproducibility. In this section, we summarize the conclusions of this work as well as propose further approaches for future research.

We trained the Transformer Groove Infilling for three different tasks: infilling closed hi-hats, jointly infilling kicks and snares, and infilling a pattern without an instrument specification. For the task of infilling closed hi-hats, we obtain a moderately good accuracy (75.4%). In order to evaluate the performance of the MSO audio representation, we train an identical model with a symbolic input, and find that the MSO only entails a 4.3% decrease in hit prediction accuracy. In the task of infilling

kicks and snares, we find that the accuracy improves to 83.4%. We assume that this improvement is caused by two main factors: a larger training dataset (4 times larger) and the benefit of learning to infill two instruments jointly. However, in the learning curves, we observed a gap between validation and training loss, likely caused by an overly specific training dataset. Finally, in the infilling random experiment we infill patterns that had previously removed random hits from their original scores, without attending to the instrument they belong to. We train two different versions of the model, one that removes between 10% and 30% of the initial hits and one that removes between 40% and 70%. Both experiments achieve very high accuracies, 97.7% and 94.7% respectively. These high accuracies are likely due to the size of the dataset (4 times larger than in the closed hi-hat task) However, since the training datasets are generated by removing random hits of the score, the musical relevance of this model remains questionable.

Overall, although the velocities appear to be adequately predicted, the microtiming dynamics (offsets) are not well captured by the model. While the metrics appear to be correct (the MSE is low and decays during training), in the heatmaps we observe very low offset ranges, i.e., the hits are generated very closely to the timestep mark. More general limitations persist: the model has been trained only with items with a 4-4 time signature and with a 2-bar fixed length. Moreover, the final objective of an infilling system is to serve as a tool for composition and hence, controls strategies as well as an user interface is still needed for usage and subjective evaluation.

6.2 Further work

Besides the aforementioned limitations, during the course of this thesis we also identified possible lines of work for further development of the Transformer Groove Infilling.

6.2.1 Multitask learning

In the predicted velocity heatmaps presented in Chapter 5, we observed that the clusters (red areas, indicating high hit density) generally appeared centered to the timestep axis, that is, with very low offsets, as opposed to the ground truth heatmaps' clusters, that displayed larger offsets. It therefore appears that the offsets and thus, the microtiming dynamics, are not being learnt adequately. Still, in all experiments, the offset MSE is lower than the velocity MSE¹, whilst the velocity range visually appears to be more adequately predicted².

Our initial approach to improve the offset prediction was normalizing the losses by their first epoch value so that all losses had similar or comparable magnitudes, as noted in Section 3.4.1. This resulted in a slight improvement in the offset prediction but in turn, the models tended to predict empty patterns, i.e., were not able to predict the hits accurately³. In this regard, we opted for the hit loss penalty factor (w , also introduced in Section 3.4.1), that improved the models prone to generate empty patterns, but as seen, still appears to be unable to predict the microtiming dynamics.

A magnitude scaling issue or in general, a code mistake in which the model is learning properly but the final output offset magnitudes are not the adequate, is not to be disregarded, but assuming this is not the case, an interesting approach could be to predict the hits, velocity and offsets in a multitask fashion. Multitask models jointly learn to perform several tasks on the assumption that there is an statistical relationship between the tasks (i.e., there is knowledge to be shared across them, as in, for example, drum transcription and beat detection [67]). Such models often

¹These two magnitudes are comparable since both have an absolute range of 1 and the MSE is a relative error measure.

²If given enough data, since in the Infilling Closed Hi-hats experiment showed limited velocity ranges in the heatmaps when compared to the equivalent ground truth heatmaps.

³It should be noted that in order to predict an offset or velocity correctly, a hit has to be predicted correctly first. This normalization of the losses fiasco suggests that the model needs to prioritize learning the hits before learning the offsets or velocities.

achieve a greater statistical strength and generalization [4]. Multitask models can be divided into two parts: (1) Generic parameters, shared across all the tasks and (2) Task-specific parameters, which only benefit from the examples of their task.

The implementation of this approach in the Transformer Groove Infilling Architecture (described in Section 3.3) would consist in splitting the output layer into three different layers, each outputting the corresponding hits, velocity and offset matrices. The input layer and encoder blocks parameters would be learnt jointly, whilst the parameters at the output split blocks would be learnt specifically to each task.

A related approach is the one by Hsiao et al. [68], in the context of music generation with tokenized sequences with the Transformer Architecture. Since the tokens in the sequence refer to different types of symbolic notation (e.g., tempo, chord, velocity, bar), Hsiao et al. add a layer after the Transformer decoder that passes each token through a different layer depending on its type (“token type-specific feed-forward heads”). In contrast, in the context of piano performance generation, Wu et al. [32], train four Transformer-XL [30] jointly for learning a 4-valued note representation, but sum the resulting 4 losses at the end, in a single-task but ‘multi-architecture’ approach. This strategy implies a higher computational cost due to the training of multiple Transformers, and hence, for the problem of this thesis, the multitask approach described above appears to be more adequate.

6.2.2 Data augmentation techniques

In the Infilling Kicks And Snares experiment, we observed a significant gap between the training loss and the validation loss. This appears to be due to an overly specific dataset, resulting from the data processing strategy described in Section 3.5.2. The derived training dataset contains items with different incomplete versions of the same performance: (A) without kick, (B) without snare, and (C) without kick and snare. However, the accuracy in the hit prediction in this experiment is considerably higher

(+8%)⁴ than in the case of the Infilling Closed Hi-hat experiment, which suggests that a larger dataset helps improving the performance of the problem, even if the training dataset is overly specific as described before.

The issue of an overly specific training dataset appears to be similar to the transformation overfitting problem described by Mignot and Peters [66] in the context of data augmentation for the music genre classification task. In their research, they find that training a model with augmented data with a single transformation (e.g. adding noise) performed better in validation datasets with the same transformation than in validation datasets without that transformation, so that the model appeared to be learning the transformation. As a solution, they chain different transformations on the data with the purpose of making the transformation ‘less obvious’ to the model and hence avoid the transformation overfitting and indeed obtain higher accuracies on non-augmented data. Inspired by that solution, we suspect that a strategy to generate a less specific training dataset could be to add an additional transformation after removing instruments from the original performance. Besides forcing the pattern to be synthesized with a different soundfont, minor perturbations to the offset values and the velocity values could help making it harder for the model to identify that different items are incomplete versions of the same performance. Additionally, some hits from the other voices could be removed. Finally, performing audio data augmentation transformations, such as adding noise or compressing the sound with different encodings, could also improve the robustness of the model for different kinds of audio inputs. Since the MSO is a direct audio representation, the audio does not need to come strictly from a drum kit but from any kind of sound source with high transients and a percussive nature.

⁴These accuracies are not directly comparable since they are obtained in different tasks and other factors besides the dataset size should be taken into account, such as hyperparameter configuration and more importantly, the role of the instrument in the drum kit language. However, since the difference is considerable and the Infilling Kicks And Snares experiment is trained in a 4 times larger dataset, we assume the dataset augmentation to be a relevant factor in the accuracy improvement.

Another approach proposed by He et al. [69] is to train the model with augmented data and in the last training epochs, switch to real data or less augmented data. They find this to improve the generalization of the model and perform better on non-augmented inputs (“data augmentation as a regularization”). A combination of this strategy with the described above could maybe improve the validation loss for the Infilling Kicks And Snares.

6.2.3 A more musically meaningful Infilling Random task

In the Infilling Random High experiment, up to 70% of the hits in the GMD performance are randomly removed, as described in Section 3.5.3. As a result, some of the input patterns consist of a small number of hits which are most likely not musically meaningful. For the purpose of having the system in a compositional setting, we would prefer a model that is more responsive to musical inputs that a composer would give. However, the high accuracy results indicate that the model is successfully performing the task. Perhaps a good strategy to keep the good accuracy results but to adapt the model to more musically meaningful inputs, and hence, more real scenarios, would be to fine-tune the model on patterns removing hits that do not appear so often in a genre pattern, i.e., sampling from the ‘colder’ areas in the heatmaps. We guess that this approach could generate more real inputs (i.e., more similar to the ones a composer would give), and hence, train the model on predicting ‘decorations’ to standard or usual patterns, resulting in more interesting infilling suggestions as a co-compositional agent.

6.2.4 Content variability

As noted in Chapter 1, one main application of an infilling system is to provide suggestions or even serve as co-creator in a compositional setting. Besides a user friendly interface, a major issue persists for this purpose: the content variability. As most architectures used for music generation [5], the Transformer Architecture is

deterministic: during inference, the same input will always produce the same output. Such inflexibility might not be the desired behavior for a model that is intended to assist creation or encourage creativity. The output layer of the Transformer architecture is a probability distribution in the hits, from which we select the hits that have an associated value above a threshold. This threshold value could indeed be a parameter controlled by the user, but still, given an input and a fixed threshold, the model would still generate the same output. In order to introduce stochasticity and hence, variability in the generation [5], a simple approach is sampling from the output probability distribution by generating a pseudorandom value for each hit position and comparing it to the value generated by the model. If, at certain timestep for a certain instrument, the value generated by the model is greater, a hit is set in that score position. Controlling the pseudorandom distribution function could give the user some control on the degree of generated content variability. Furthermore, conditioning such as on genre or style could also be considered for a more controllable tool.

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